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IS THE NATIONAL POLICE OF UKRAINE EUROPEAN?

(ABSTRACT, KEY WORDS)

The fact that the National Police of Ukraine, which is territorially European, does not yet testify to the possibility today to consider the National Police as the European Ukrainian police in the sense of its internal readiness to conform to the standards of organization and operation of the police forces of the European Commonwealth. The answer to this problem can be solved by such tasks as searching for the principles of "Europeanization" of the National Police in the current legislation; perception and display in the media of the European fundamentals of the National Police; analysis of the status of self-identification of the National Police as a European and supporting European and Euro-Atlantic integration as an element of its own "Europeanization" by Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine. According to the results of the study, it is shown that the term "European Ukrainian police" was used by the leadership of the state and the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, as well as the term "new police of Ukraine", solely in order to maintain the image, and was not widely disseminated either in Ukraine or in the world. At the same time, a new law enforcement agency was expected in Ukraine. The main reason for this was the hope of getting high-level police officers like in the European police forces. But the "transfer" of borrowed positive experience and methods of effective work of the police authorities of Europe to Ukraine did not take place and could not have happened due to a number of objective reasons. However, the principles of the European and Euro-Atlantic trend regarding the future of the National Police of Ukraine have already been laid down and for that, it's will taken place, we must consider the following basic realities: 1. National police cannot be a permanent beneficiary of funds and police technologies from the European Union – it is necessary to develop internal human, technical and intellectual resources and integrate into the legal circle of the police community of European countries on the principles of an equal partnership. The stated European integration is fully possible only after building a proper economic basis in the state. 2. The Ukrainian police will acquire the conditional status of a European one only when its corporate mentality and the mentality of the average policeman become European. In other words, the National Police of Ukraine must be not only professionally "self-identify" as a European, but also be recognized as such. Any artificial imposition of the image of the European Police without real changes is not promising.

Key words: *European trend and European status; National Police of Ukraine; European and Euro-Atlantic integration*

Problem statement

For quite a long time, the website of one of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine's higher education institutions has been hosting an information banner, which invites everyone to become an officer of the *European Ukrainian police*. This should be recognized as such a rather original innovation, even taking into account the fact that at the time of its creation the National Police of Ukraine for a long time was called the New Police.

By the way, this *practice of naming the police as "new" was not an invention of Ukraine* –

Beth K. Greener once stated that in 2009, in El Salvador, Cambodia and Haiti, the police reform resulted in "*a new national civilian police force being completely independent of the armed forces and under civilian control*", that "*this new international police force implies an increase in the willingness and ability of actors to carry out police operations in other jurisdictions in certain situations, both in terms of interim law enforcement of force and in terms of long-term development programs*" [1, p. 110]. Also R. Spencer Kidd already now remembers the new *German National Police* (Police

in Order) of 1936, or the abolition of the entire local police of Iceland and its transfer to the *new National Police* in 1972 [2, p. 6, 13]. A striking sign of the present can also be considered the creation in 2013 of the *new national police force "Politie"* in the Netherlands [3], etc.

As for Ukraine, the *priority of the name "European Ukrainian police"* probably belongs to the former Prime Minister of Ukraine A. Yatsenyuk, who at the beginning of April 2015, long before the appearance of the police itself, "noted that the bills on the reform of the Ministry of Internal Affairs provide for clear rights and powers of the police officer: "We are taking a big step in the real reform of the former Soviet police system and the transition to the *European Ukrainian police* – in terms of content, form and value" [4]. At the same time, as it can be seen, but it is in this phrase – "*European Ukrainian Police*" – that no one in the world calls the National Police of Ukraine. Perhaps, this term is intended only for internal, as well as "New Police", image use. In addition, a certain warning is caused by a rather categorical statement in 2016 by L. Belkin that "European powers cannot be granted to the Ukrainian police" [5].

At the same time, the very fact of existence of the National Police of Ukraine, which is at least territorial European, obliges to take a preventive approach to the perception of the National Police as a law enforcement agency of the European state, and the *confirmation of the possibility to consider it as European Ukrainian police in terms of its internal readiness to comply with the standards of organization and operation of the European Community police bodies, define the purpose of the article*. Although, in our opinion, the sign of "Europeanity" is rather mental in nature and cannot serve as another good sticker. By the way, a certain *understanding of the essence of "Europeanity"* is provided by the mass media, which in relation to the same National Police can be partially transformed into a feeling of security, "service, quality of service, and quality of services provided", tolerance [6]; it can even be a question of passing the "European test" [7], or "European standards and philosophy" [8]. I. Gerasimov, together with his co-authors, doctrinally *understands "Europeanity" as a form of institutional embodiment, a framework phenomenon, the status* [9, p. 138, 141–142].

Proceeding from this, the novelty of the article lies in the author's view of the problem, which has not been previously studied, and the tasks are contained in the search for the basis of "Europeanization" of the National Police in the current legisla-

tion; perception and reflection in the media of the European principles of the National Police; analysis of the state of self-identification of the National Police as European and support of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine of European and Euro-Atlantic integration as an element of their own "Europeanization".

As for the scientific roots of the problem, among such today as applied to the militia, police and European cooperation, one can name a comparative legal analysis of the organizational and legal framework of the police (militia) of Germany, Poland and Ukraine by A.S. Pronevich [10]; doctrinal approach to the European model of police (militia) as the goal of achieving the purpose of reforming the internal affairs of Ukraine by I.V. Zozulia [11]; the basics of civil police management by A.A. Telichkin [12]; the specifics of European police and criminal law cooperation on the example of Swedish studies in European law by Bergström M. and Jonsson Cornell A. [13]; a framework for the establishment and functioning of police forces and their cooperation among themselves and with EU bodies, such as Europol, in order to prevent and resolve cross-border crimes by Vikström R.D. [14], etc. With regard to the development of the security and defence sector, which has an impact on the development of the National Police as a European police force, this is the investigation "European Integration of Ukraine: Internal Factors and External Influences" by the Razumkov Centre [15] and others, which are fundamental to the problems of European integration and the development of the National Police as a European police force.

Searching for the basis of the "Europeanization" of the National Police in existing legislation

First of all, in the search for European signs in the police of Ukraine it is necessary to refer to the current legislation, as it forms the only legal basis for the organization and activities of the National Police of Ukraine.

On the one hand, it can be noted that any *lack of significant and fruitful contacts with the European police authorities* (and only with them in the areas of activity, it makes sense to compare the National Police of Ukraine) and acquired practical experience does not make it automatically European – as well as the lack of language practice with native speakers indicates gaps in its study. Conversely, the presence of such contacts allows us to hope for what we want. But does the basic legal and regulatory framework provide for such "Europeanization" of the National Police? Does it contain

a note on the state policy of perception of the National Police of Ukraine as a European police force?

It should be noted that in contrast to the European character as a status attribute, in the widest case "Europeanization", according to A. Illarionov, is "the process of dissemination of customs, habits, standards (regardless of their political and legal nature) available in European countries", to which we can also add – and *the acquisition of these customs, habits, standards*. Therefore, since the European police work according to the same relevant standards, *the Europeanization of the Ukrainian police can be understood as the process of integration of the National Police of Ukraine into the legal circle of the police community of European countries on the basis of an equal partner*.

In the meantime, according to paragraphs 32–34 of the Regulations on the National Police under the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine dated 28.10.2015 No. 877 [16], the National Police, in accordance with the tasks assigned to it, "represents and ensures the implementation of Ukraine's obligations in the International Criminal Police Organization – Interpol and the European Police Office (Europol)", "organizes interaction of law enforcement and other state bodies of Ukraine with Interpol, Europol, and also enters information from law enforcement agencies of Ukraine into these databases.

But is cooperation with Europol a direct sign that the National Police of Ukraine is European? Unfortunately, neither in the Law of Ukraine "On the National Police" [17], nor in the Regulation on the National Police [16] there is no such thing at all – the closest cooperation with Europol, as it seems, is carried out "in accordance with the tasks assigned to it (the National Police. – Author.)", as in the title of paragraph 4 of the Regulation [16]. And the formulation of such tasks could be seen as a distant and veiled *basis for the Europeanization of the National Police only in subparagraphs 1 and 2 of paragraph 3 of the said Regulation* – it is "implementation of public policy" and "ensuring the formation of public policy". At the same time, it is quite clear that the spheres of protection of human rights and freedoms, interests of society and the state, crime prevention, maintenance of public security and order, which *are voiced in p. 1 p. 3, are exclusively internal*.

Therefore, only considering the state policy as "practical activity of political subjects and public authorities to implement the developed political course and achieve specific political goals", as not-

ed by Y.V. Kovbasiuk and his co-authors, as a type of its activity only the fourth (international) level brings into contact with the UN, UNESCO, EU, NATO, CIS, etc. [18, p. 12, 13] – that is, as applied to the National Police of Ukraine, it can somehow be conventionally close to the European one.

We believe that the European Commission, the Organization for Security and Cooperation in Europe and its Parliamentary Assembly, the Council of Europe, the Association of European Border Regions, Eurovoisko, the Carpathian Euroregion, the Mediterranean Union, the Nordic Passport Union and the NATO Southeast European Initiative can be referred to the category of "other" international European organizations in the direction of the National Police of Ukraine. Although NATO is not a law enforcement agency, its values of democracy, individual freedom, the rule of law, etc., are shared by the National Police of Ukraine (Art. 1, 6 of the Law of Ukraine "On the National Police" of 02.07.2015 No. 580–VIII [17]).

At the same time, this thesis has already been partially developed in the work "International Police Cooperation: A Global Perspective" edited by Daniel J. Koenig and Dilip K. Das, which is a modern and detailed account of the new international joint initiatives of the time [19].

The media on the European principles of the National Police

It should be noted that the emergence of a new law enforcement agency – the police – became a certain event in the life of the state, presented as an element of the long-awaited reform of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine. In this regard, P. Poroshenko noted on 25.08.2015 that "we are a European country *and the police are a key attribute of the European country*" [20]. We can agree that this is the right position on a case-by-case basis, but, firstly, as a "key attribute of a European country", the National Police of Ukraine at that time could be perceived only as a promising deposit, because no significant results could be attributed to it by definition. Secondly, the President's perception of the police as a "key attribute" may not be indicative of the secondary role the police should play in the country. And, thirdly, the reference to the "Europeanity" of our state can unwittingly cover the National Police with the "Europeanity" in advance. This was the starting point for media publications on the emergence and formation of the National Police of Ukraine.

At the same time, in our opinion, it is necessary to distinguish three main time periods during which the meaning and context of publications on

the appearance and results of the National Police activity changed significantly. Firstly, it is a period of euphoria at the end of 2015, when the pages of the media practically did contain exalted articles and photographs about the new Ukrainian police – about the sharp age "rejuvenation" of the personnel; about its new, Western style, appearance; about the transition to new methods, principles and standards of work; about the provision of foreign patrol vehicles; about the prospects of work in the police and so on. For example, these are publications such as "The traffic police will work until the new police arrive", "The police will be fully operational only after all amendments to the legislation of Ukraine have been made", "Love of Kyiv citizens for the new police", "What the new patrol police will be made of: uniforms, ammunition and transport", "On the State Flag Day in Lviv the new police will start working" and others. Along with them there were also warning publications – "Eka Zguladze. I don't like it very much when the system starts to hide behind the process", "Externally the police, inside – the cops", etc.

In general, 2016 was marked by a gradual adaptation of the population to the police, its comparison with the previous militia force and exposure of shortcomings in its work. Correspondingly, the names of the then publications in the media were also given: "How does the police reform look from the inside? Talk to the deputy head of the personnel department of the National Police of Lviv region", "Crime statistics. The police started to register absolutely all the appeals – Decanoidze," "On the real police", "Zguladze. Patrol police already annoys me. This is a sinking "island" without comprehensive reform", "EU experience: why the new police should learn to hear the public", etc.

In 2017 and the beginning of the next, 2018, not only did the police and the police "lick" each other, but they were also characterized by more intrusive requirements for still low professionalism and significant gaps and current problems in the work of "politsiantov"¹. Therefore, are characteristic of and the names of media publications, such as: "Police malpractice. At present, the police are short of 20,000 officers", "Presentation at Recruitment to the Patrol Police", "Do new police officers take bribes? Confession of a Patrol Officer", "Police Reform Victory or Failure", "Police Training. The sys-

¹ By the way, Russian philologists insist on such naming of police officers, in contrast to their Russian translation [21].

tem of training of future police officers will be radically changed" and others.

It should be noted that the appearance of the police in Ukraine instead of the militia brought with it for the general public in their subjective understanding, not only its demonstrative European features (the same uniform of the American model, cars – from Japan), but also signs of future new changes. And the media quite accurately reflected not only hope, but also the excitement of society in this regard. One can say that the media even "clashed" with the position of the positive image of the police and the reality of its imperfection imposed by the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine [22]. Although, as the expert of the Center for Political and Legal Reforms A. Banchuk notes, "the general level of sociological trust or distrust is formed through the media, the television picture. *It does not reflect objectively whether the police and a particular police unit have become better at work, in which territory or not*" [23]. Therefore, perhaps because of the existing problems with the police, the domestic media today not only do not remember any "Europeanity" of the National Police, but avoid it altogether. As for the foreign media, they do not need to do so at all.

For the sake of objectivity, we can also look at the publications of the mass media with regard to the similar *"European dimension" of the now former militia*. It should be admitted that there were many more of them. For example, in 2007, the media spoke about "Reforming the police force in the mirror of European policing – what we do wrong" [24], and later – "Speaking and acting in a European way. Dnipropetrovsk police are preparing for Euro 2012", "Mogilev: We have a Soviet militia force – we need to make it European", "Expert: Ukrainian militia is much more tolerant of European police", "MIA: The experiment will show how ready the police are to European standards of activity". Here one can even see the confirmation of the thesis that "the expectations of the European police were more fascinating than any reality".

The state of self-identification of the National Police as a European police

Now, after more than two years of its existence, the questions of self-determination, self-perception and self-perception, which can be components of the concept of self-identification, the National Police of Ukraine as a European police force, are of some interest. And although S. Datsyuk believes that these processes are not identical (quoted by O.K. Romanchuk [25]), but still, in our opinion, have signs of some synonymy. At the same time,

A.S. Moshenskyy associates the question of a policeman's self-identification with his political consciousness [26, p. 211]. More profound general questions of European identity as a supranational concept and the basis of the Charter for European Identity are doctrinally considered by M.A. Kozlovets in his paper "The Phenomenon of National Identity: Challenges of Globalization" [27, p. 351–375].

It should be taken into account that the term "self-identification" usually applies to a person. But in the case of the National Police, as the central executive authority, this term can be considered within the framework of "corporate self-identification", since it fully corresponds both to the desire and to the measures to form a collective perception not only of the National Police but also of the public about the police. Although the purpose of the study *can only be relevant to us with regard to the facts of self-image of the National Police as a European police force*. And, as N.A. Grebeniuk notes, "self-identification is exactly the component of identity that can act (in the optimal case) as a catalyst of the process of identity restructuring in accordance with new social requirements" [28, p. 227]. An important consideration, according to Ben Bradford, Paul Quinton, Andy Myhill and Gillian Porter, is to encourage police officers to change organizational and personal practices related to group identity in organizational justice models and classic problems with respect to "cop culture", as well as the risk of overidentification with the organization and counter-productive types of compliance that may arise [29].

Therefore, something can be seen as a positive impact on the level of perceived self-identification of the National Police a year ago by the Razumkov Center that "in Ukraine to such social institutions as... police Ukrainian-speaking respondents have great confidence" [30]. Although, based on the lack of significant socio-psychological research in this area, we can consider that the self-determination, self-perception and self-awareness of the National Police of Ukraine as a European police does not extend beyond the important, traditionally typical for domestic law enforcement agencies, not "local" problems – the professional development and professional motivation of its staff. While the stay of a young man in a police position should already be a preventive synonym for her high professional training, a kind of marker of professionalism. This, hopefully, temporary *imbalance does not yet allow us to speak of true European self-determination, self-perception and self-awareness* of an ordinary policeman on the basis of European identity. At the same time, the leadership of the Ministry and the

National Police takes a different, more optimistic position, hoping for the solidarity of the police authorities in Europe and speaking about the interaction and implementation of the latest European practices in the activities of the National Police of Ukraine.

Support of the Ukrainian Interior Ministry for European and Euro-Atlantic integration as an element of "Europeanization"

This is the name given to the section of the Annual (2017) Report of the Project Office of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine [31], which was created "to give the Ministry additional support during its transformation into a modern European-style law enforcement agency...". In particular, it was reported that on 14.12.2016 an agreement on strategic cooperation between Ukraine and Europol was signed (development of analytical reports and establishment of joint investigation teams with the EU member states); "Completion of work on development of draft laws and amendments to the Regulations of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine on the implementation of EU directives on the transportation of dangerous goods and driver's licenses"; "The project "Management of migration and asylum processes" was signed (creation of a European-style migration management system); "The Ministry of Internal Affairs also joined the project"; "The MIA has also joined the NATO Force Planning and Evaluation Process (FPEP) and consulted on the development of new objectives, including: a) planning and budgeting; b) interoperability; c) cyber defence; and d) gender perspectives.

At the same time, as it is seen, so far the "Support of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine for European and Euro-Atlantic integration" is acquiring signs of mainly unilateral preferences from the EU, where the beneficiary is the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine. It is quite understandable that such a *policy*, which is aimed only at obtaining the latest police technologies, financial or technical support from EU countries, is not an equal partnership, but requires appropriate counter steps. Therefore, it would be quite appropriate here, after more than a year of existence of the "project office", to put forward the slogan "Through training – to a real partnership" and search for opportunities for more active participation with its proposals in the interests of the EU. Moreover, taking into account the fact that so far the *positive for the EU "Support..." on the part of Ukraine* is limited only to "the functions of the National Contact Point for the organization of interaction between the public authorities of Ukraine and the European Office for the

Prevention of Abuse and Fraud, the European Commission and the European Court of Auditors", within which 25-29.07.2017 "the correct use of European funds during the implementation of one of the EU projects was checked".

A similar foreign "donor" can now be considered as the European Union Advisory Mission (EUMM), which since 2014 has been assisting, among other state bodies, also the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine and the National Police "in the consistent reform of the civil security sector through strategic advice and practical support to reform activities in line with EU standards and international principles of good governance and human rights" [32]. Only the latest of its activities can be named, such as "The mobile unit of the EUMM starts its work in Poltava with representatives of the public and local authorities" (18.04.2018), "European and Canadian police officers conduct trainings on personal security for the National Police of Ukraine" (03.04.2018), "Lead by example – The EUMM conducted leadership training for senior police officials" (26.03.2018), "Technical support of the EUMM will help the police in information and analysis and fight against cybercrime" (15.02.2018), etc.

The most important now from the point of view of aspiration to "Europeanization" of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine can be considered the introduction of the *post of the Deputy Minister for European Integration and the creation of the website of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs of Ukraine of the section "Eurointegration"* with the tabs "Association Agreement", "Visa Dialogue", "Cooperation with the EU", "Recommendations of the Parliamentary Assembly of the Council of Europe".

Today, the *Department of International Cooperation and European Integration* also functions within the structure of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, which, as reported, "participates in the formation of the main directions of state policy in the field of international cooperation, in particular, European and Euro-Atlantic integration, ensures the implementation of tasks and functions assigned to the Ministry of Internal Affairs... in the formation of state policy on international cooperation and control over the implementation of state policy in the field of international cooperation issues by structural subdivisions of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, territorial bodies, institutions, institutions and enterprises belonging to the sphere of management of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the National Guard of Ukraine, central executive authorities, the activities of which are directed and coordinated by the Minister of Internal Affairs" [33].

Without detailing excessive attention to the *lack of mention of "Euro-Atlantic integration" in the name of the Department* contrary to the sixth task of the Department and with reference to the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine in terms of its powers, it should be recalled the remark of I.V. Yakovyuk that the *integration process is exclusively in the European Union, it is a schematic sequence of such stages as a free trade zone → customs union → common market → monetary union → political integration*; and that *EU integration* also understands, among other things, the existence of supranational institutions, the delegation to EU institutions of the right to exercise certain sovereign rights and a wide range of powers, a single legal personality, etc. [34, p. 5–8]. This explains why today a separate department or ministry is not able to "form the main directions of state policy in the field of European and Euro-Atlantic integration". That is, operating with no longer applicable concepts of basis and superstructure, *one can expect European integration, and hence – and "Europeanization" of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine or the National Police – as a result of the work of the corresponding Department of the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine, will be possible only after building an appropriate economic basis in the state.*

Somewhat more effective practical developments in the direction of "Europeanization" of the National Police, in our opinion, are in the assets of the Department of International Police Cooperation of the National Police [35], representing Ukraine in Interpol and since 2010 and in Europol, actively provides the creation of the *image of the European Ukrainian police*, and the activities of which require a separate study.

Conclusions

Thus, summarizing the results, it can be noted that the name "European Ukrainian Police", introduced in 2015 by the leadership of the state and the Ministry of Internal Affairs of Ukraine in relation to the newly created National Police of Ukraine, has not been widely spread in Ukraine today. At the same time, the deep meaning of the name fully met the then expectations of the population from the emergence of a new law enforcement agency. In particular, the most important of them is the desire to get highly qualified police in Ukraine, like the police of European countries. Unfortunately, the short-term conditional "transfer" of someone else's positive experience and methods of effective work of the police authorities of European countries in the territory of Ukraine has not occurred and could

not occur for a number of quite objective reasons. Nevertheless, the foundations of the European and Euro-Atlantic trend regarding the future of the National Police of Ukraine have already been laid, and in order for them to take place, it is necessary to take into account the following main realities:

1. The National Police cannot be a permanent beneficiary of EU funds and police technologies – it is necessary to develop internal human, technical and intellectual resources and to integrate into the legal framework of the European police community on the basis of equal partners. This European integration is fully possible only after building a proper economic basis in the country.

2. The Ukrainian police will acquire the condi-

tional status of European police only when its corporate mentality and mentality of an ordinary police officer becomes European. In other words, the National Police of Ukraine should not only professionally "self-identify" as a European police force, but also be recognized as such. Any artificial planting of the image of the European police without real changes is not promising.

In general, the question "is the National Police of Ukraine European?" is rhetorical. But it is too early to give an affirmative answer to this question regarding the *internal readiness of the Ukrainian police to comply with the standards of organization and activity of the European Community police bodies*.

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**THE FORMATION AND ESTABLISHMENT
OF THE SCIENTIFIC CATEGORY
OF "STATE FUNCTIONS"**

(ABSTRACT, KEY WORDS)

"State functions" is the basic scientific category of the theory of state and law that was established in the legal science through the evolution of legal, political and philosophical thought. The study of the main activities (state functions) is possible only in combination with other categories, such as state aims and state tasks, the reconceptualization of which caused the establishment of the scientific category "state functions". The purpose of the article is an in-depth analysis of the evolution of legal and political thought about the aims, tasks and functions of the state, the result of which is reflected in the novelty, which is to establish at the scientific level, the ratio of aims, tasks and functions of the state in different historical periods, and the formation of "state functions" as an important scientific category, which ensures the implementation of the social purpose of the state. The establish and transformation of scientific views coincides with historical epochs, which corresponded to the realities characteristic of a certain historical period. The state aims responded to the real social status and remained a philosophical category, because they did not find practical implementation, which was explained by the low development of legal science, and the law was not the main regulator of social relations. The revolutionary period in the development of the doctrine of "state functions" was a Modern Period, which was characterized by the formation of constitutionalism and was associated with European law schools. In addition to the establishment of new categories, such as state tasks and state functions. Scientists of the Modern Period have been improved philosophical, abstract doctrine of the state goals and were laid the scientific foundations of a democratic, liberal, rule of law state. In the research of the state functions, the great importance had the work of domestic legal scholars of the late 19th – early 20th centuries, in which the whole state was finally formed as a political category, which is reflected in the aims, and should be implemented through the function. As of today, the aims and tasks have become correlated and express the social purpose of the state, which has found its consolidation at the constitutional level. "State functions", having a relationship with the tasks ensure the implementation of its social purpose.

Key words: *state; state goals; state objectives; state functions; political thought; state power; legal thought*

Problem statement

Many scientific concepts and categories pass a considerable way of the formation, and the legal science is a striking example of that. As a result of the evolution of the meaning, essence of political and legal thought and the development of society, many concepts have passed their way from an ephemeral philosophical idea to a complex legal category. John Gering emphasizes: "Concepts are not static. Work on the subject necessarily includes the reconceptualization of the subject, and progress in the sciences is due to changes in concepts and definitions" [1, p.35].

Such a scientific category as "state functions" is a striking example of such a long-term and

complex process of forming and establishment in the legal science. The state acts for the aims for which it originated. The main directions of its activity are called "state functions". In "state functions" are realized the state will, power of the state, and state activity. Functions are determined by the main tasks of the state and may be different in different states, and the same state at different stages of its development [2, p.100].

The most important aims and directions of activity of the state, at one or another stage of development of the latter, are stipulated by economic, political, social and other conditions of its existence. Based on this, the main directions of its activities

are objective, due to the needs of the civil society. Implementation of the main activities of the state has a permanent, systematic nature, which takes place within a certain time of the existence of individual tasks that require a common solution from the state, to meet the needs of society and preserve it as a whole legal institute of state [3, p.83].

All functional activities of the modern state are aimed at achieving the general aim: the welfare of man, his moral, material and physical well-being, maximum legal and social protection of the individual. The state must always act as the supreme defender of the legitimate interests of the individual [4, p.124].

To date, the formation and establishment of the scientific category "state functions" was made possible by the evolution of legal, political and philosophical thought, starting from Plato and Aristotle. The active stage of its development was associated with the world's social transformations of the Modern Period, in particular, with such tracts as "The Spirit of the Laws" by Charles de Montesquieu, "Two Treatises of Government" by John Locke, who based their teachings on the theory of separation of powers. Georg Jellinek in his work "General Doctrine of Law and State" developed a theory of correlation of state functions and functions of public authority. In domestic science firstly allocate pre-revolutionary period by which M.M. Korkunov concluded about the formality of the aims and tasks of the state, and S.A. Kotlyarevsky delimited the aims, tasks and functions of the state. In the Soviet Union era scientific direction is connected with doctrines of A.M. Vasilyev, A.I. Denisov, G.N. Manov. Among foreign scholars can be called Brain Tamcinaha, Charles Howard McIlwain, M.J. Vile – their doctrines about state functions based mainly on constitutional principles, and concentrated to ensure of human rights.

In view of this, the purpose of the article is to in-depth analysis of the evolution of legal and political thought about aims, tasks and functions of the state, the result of which is reflected in the novelty, which consists in the establishment on the scientific level the ratio of aims, tasks and functions of the state in different historical periods, and the formation of "state functions" as an important scientific category, which ensures the fulfillment of the social purpose of the state. Achievement of the aim is based on the tasks of analysis of political and legal thought about state aims: from Ancient Times to Modern Period, research of development of the doctrines about

functions and aims of the state during the Modern Period, and establishment of category "state functions" in the works lawyers of the late 19 – early 20 centuries, and in the domestic legal science.

Political and legal thoughts about aims of the state: from Ancient Times to Modern Period

Ideas about the aims of the state were largely formed in Ancient Greece, in particular for understanding the nature of human and his place in society. Also Ancient Greece we owe the formation of the Western legal tradition, the ideas of constitutionalism, the development of methods of management and the principles of its limitation [5, p.10].

On a more qualitative level, the doctrine of the ideal just state was formed by Plato in the dialogue "The Republic". When he constructed the state, he believed in the possibility of practical implementation of his project. Plato speaks of the correspondence of the five types of government – aristocracy, timocracy, oligarchy, democracy and tyranny, according to the five types of the spiritual state of people. Under this opposes ideal-aristocratic where a common and the main aim can be point to justice, which must become the basis of all spheres of four other – vicious (immoral). Here, in turn, the aims in each state structure of their own, based on a certain public abundance, to which we do not aspire to, that in the end and lose this system, such a boon in timocracy – military successes, in oligarchy – wealth, democracy – freedom. It is also worth noting that Plato believed tyranny the worst kind of state structure, dominated by lawlessness, arbitrariness and violence, without highlighting of aims [6, p.52–55].

The logical continuation of the ideas of Ancient Greece found its followers in Ancient Rome. The main achievements of Roman philosophers and lawyers were the division into public and private law and the creation of the concept of written law [7, p.46]. It is necessary to highlight the famous speaker, philosopher and political figure – Marcus Tullius Cicero and his famous treatise "De Re Publica", which was written in the philosophical form of the dialogue with direct references to "The Republic" by Plato.

Marcus Tullius Cicero proceeds from the common ideas to supporters of aristocracy about the natural origin of the state. Civil communities arise not by establishment, because by nature for humans are endowed by the gods with a desire for communion. The first reason for uniting people into a state was "not so much their weakness as their innate need to live together". But the state (respublica) Cicero defines not only as a natural

organism, but also as an artificial formation, as a cause, the property of the people (*res populi*), "the people – not an institution". By the people is understood "the union of many people, bound together by agreement in matters of law and community of interests." Accordingly, law is the basis of the state, and the state itself is not only a moral, but also a legal community. Thus, Marcus Tullius Cicero stands at the origins of the legal concept of the state, which later had many followers, up to the modern supporters of the idea of the rule of law. Cicero paid great attention to the analysis of various forms of government, the search for the "best" form. The aim of the state is to protect the property interests of citizens. Protection of property is one of the reasons for its formation. Cicero characterized violation of inviolability of private and state property as desecration and violation of justice and law [8, p.47–48]. It is important to note that this formulation of the aim of the state indicates the emergence of those liberal ideas and concepts that are reflected in the future.

The next step in the development of ideas about the state, its aims, tasks and functions was made in the Middle Ages. Its first half is characterized by the emergence of feudalism, the strong ideological influence of Christianity and the Catholic Church on any doctrine, including legal. As for the second half of the Middle Ages, here for example the 14th century is characterized by the gradual loss of the Catholic Church of its leading role in the life of many countries of Western Europe. Inevitably a contradiction is brewing between the emerging nation states and the church. The most striking and specific theoretical expression of protest against the claims of the Catholic Church to secular power, was reflected in the teachings of democratic freedom by Marsilius of Padua, denying the presence in the Church of "coercive power". Significant popularity Marsilius of Padua received thanks to the treatise "Defensor pacis", that was written in 1324 in the spirit of medieval scholasticism. It deals with the heavenly and earthly aims of humans, laws and state. The state by Marsilius of Padua is modern, self-sufficient community, based on reason and faith people, it's not empire, but it's nation that organized as talked in the time in seigniorship. He notes that the state arises at a certain stage of human history in the process of complicating people's lives, as a result of the development of various forms of their life. The beginning of the establishment of this institution laid the family.

Following these appear cities and finally arises a state that is formed as a result of an agreement concluded between people living in the same territory. The aim and purpose of this institution is protecting the interests of the population, meet their needs and expectations. With the advent of the state Marsilius of Padua indicates actually there is a political power that was not before. The state for it is a secular institution or speaking in modern language – the political organization of society, created by humanity at a certain stage of history. "The state's final aim is to care for the benefit of the population" [9, p.44–45].

It is worth to note that a significant contribution to the theory of the state was made by many other scientists and philosophers of their time, such as Augustine of Hippo, Niccolo Machiavelli, Jean Bodin, Thomas Hobbes, Hugo Grotius and other. But all the doctrines about the aims of the state before a certain historical period had a philosophical and abstract character, were only certain ideas and concepts and did not find practical implementation.

We have to note that the aim of the state remained such an ephemeral category, and received a political character only in the future. Here a special place is occupied by the doctrine about objectivity aims of the state by Georg Jellinek, which usually distinguish one, from a variety of historically altered functions of the respective state and declare its essential aim only this state, and it is declared by its special place. Such specific aims recognized for example: Ancient Rome – foreign conquests, for England – political freedom, for Spain of Habsburgs period – the restoration of the unity of faith, for Germany – the kingdom of freedom (by Johann Gottlieb Fichte), for Russia – the colonization and acculturation of Northern Asia. In broad circles of society this theory has a significant role, especially when it comes to international relations [10, p.239]. More relevant for our time and research example we can see for example in the Constitution of the Soviet Union (1977). In the preamble of the Constitution, a separate paragraph is devoted to the aim of the Soviet state, it is pointed that "The supreme aim of this Soviet state is the building of a classless communist society in which there will be public, communist self-government" [11, p.5].

The development of doctrines about aims and functions of the state in the period of Modern Time

The Modern Period is a revolutionary era in legal science. There was a departure from the philosophical, abstract concept about aims, tasks and

functions of the state, and ideas were developed, which in the future were reflected in practice and became the basis of progressive legal states. These ideas are primarily associated with the French and English legal schools of Modern Period. This is a period of great transformations in jurisprudence and the theory of state in particular. We can highlight the famous practicing legal scholars who have created new legal categories and ideas that are relevant today.

The creator of the ideological and political doctrine of liberalism, the English materialist philosopher John Locke, represented the state as "the general will which is the expression of the predominant force" that is the majority of citizens who "enter the state". He considered the state in the form of a set of people who were united into one whole under the beginning of the general law established by them [12, p.127]. By John Locke the state was created to guarantee natural rights (liberty, equality, property) and laws (peace and security). The state should not infringe on these rights. Natural rights have reliable guarantees. The main danger for natural rights and laws follows from privileges, especially from the privileges of the holders of power [13, p.81]. These ideas, were really revolutionary for its time, because the basis of society's life were laid the foundations of a legal state, which influenced the formation and development of states in the world. John Locke made an incredible step forward in the development of theory of state, creating the doctrine of the legal state, with the list of rights that are guaranteed by the state, and in this case it is possible to talk about systematic departure from philosophical abstract ideas, and about the origin of new categories such as state tasks and state functions.

A huge influence on legal science and the development of liberal and democratic ideas influenced the doctrines of Charles de Montesquieu which is largely a follower of John Locke. The doctrine of the state, in particular about the aims and functions, is based on the theory of separation of powers. Charles de Montesquieu is not so much the author and founder of this theory, but he improved, developed and formulated it in such a way that it has not lost relevance for today, being the basis of the state system of most world democracies. The concept of separation of state powers according to Charles de Montesquieu is as follows: 1) the power is divided into three branches – legislative, executive, judicial each of which has its own functions; 2) each branch of government is limited to the performance of its

functions and should not interfere with the functions of other branches of government; 3) the persons who make up the bodies of these branches of government should be separated from other branches of government and cannot simultaneously perform their functions [14, p.5]. We can say that were created the foundations of the current system of checks and balances.

The doctrines of Charles de Montesquieu about the separation of powers was new in the political and legal concept: 1. Charles de Montesquieu connected the liberal understanding of freedom with the idea of constitutional consolidation of the mechanism of separation of powers. Freedom is established only by laws. 2. Charles de Montesquieu included in the powers to be distinguished the judiciary. He deduced the principle of independence of judges. The triad (legislative, executive, judicial) of powers become a classic formula of the theory of constitutionalism. Political and legal doctrine of Charles de Montesquieu about the separation of powers was directed against royal absolutism. It also served to justify the compromise of the bourgeoisie and the nobility. The doctrine of freedom, civil rights, separation of powers was enshrined in the constitutional acts of France, laid the basis for the USA Constitution, constitutions of other states and the Declaration of the Rights of Man and Citizen (1789). The political and legal doctrine of Charles de Montesquieu is considered a classical school of constitutionalism. Among moral reasons the most important are the principles of the state system. By Charles de Montesquieu the problem of rational organization of society is primarily a political and legal problem, not a social one. Freedom in the ideology of early liberalism meant a reasonable organization of the state and the rule of law. Freedom by Charles de Montesquieu is "the right to do whatever that laws permit". He associated the ideal of freedom with the consideration of existing forms of the state [13, p.100–101]. According to Charles de Montesquieu the main aim of the state is the freedom of society, which will be ensured by the rule of law.

The research of this issue is impossible without analysis state doctrine by Georg Jellinek. We have already mentioned his ideas about the objective aims of the state, which are relevant to a particular state, in a certain historical period. He combined the formal dogmatic understanding of state and law with sociology. Georg Jellinek distinguished between the social doctrine of the state and the doctrine of state law and separated the written constitution from the actual one. He argued that law is a

compromise between different conflicting interests. Power and law in the social aspect must be interpreted psychologically. The law in the social aspect and the positivity of the law are based on the average, typical belief of the people that this law is valid. On this basis the whole law and order are built [13, p.174]. Thus, Georg Jellinek became one of the founders of the concept of the social purpose of the state. As for the subjective aims of the state, they are based on the social purpose of the state and mean those aims by which the state will be a single, integral structure.

The most significant achievement of Georg Jellinek in this matter is the introduction in the scientific space of such a category as "functions of the state", which is reflected in the famous work "General Theory of the State". Examining the theory of state functions, we can conclude that the correct solution was the result of an abstract study of the state and that the progressive development of scientific thought has led to the establishment of essential state functions. The history of state law presents an extremely large number of attempts to classify these functions. But only the distinction between the three main functions of state power-legislative, Executive (administration) and the administration of justice - has acquired lasting significance, despite the diversity in the modern literature of views on the essence of the functions and the nature of their relationship. Other ephemeral classifications have lost their meaning due to the same progressive penetration into the true essence of the state, which led to the formation of a single correct view [10, p.567].

After analyzing these statements, it can be concluded that the idea of state functions is based on the concept of separation of powers. It can also be seen that the "state functions" are equated to the functions of state power, or to the functions of a particular branch of government. This is not surprising, because Georg Jellinek was a supporter of the ideas of Charles de Montesquieu and was a bright follower of him. It is worth to note that in the future, the scientific legal community will note that "the functions of the state" and "the functions of public authority" are different categories, and they cannot be identified.

The project of building a state with the help of the law has spread around the world with different and ambiguous results. The legal pluralism that existed in the Middle Ages in Western Europe was consolidated into a single system, although cultural and religious diversity was preserved outside the legal system, usually without legal status.

Outside Europe, especially in colonial and post-colonial territories, a unifying legal system was adopted that absorbed and openly recognized the multiplicity of norms and institutions [15].

Establishment of the category "state functions" in the works of lawyers of the late 19th – early 20th centuries

The establishment of the category "state functions" in the domestic legal science occurred under the significant influence of Western legal thought, has come a long way and is firmly entrenched as a scientific category. As for the national scientific space, in our opinion, it should begin with the doctrines of B.M. Chicherin. He conducted a large, relevant for the second half of the 19th century doctrine, from which several important conclusions can be identified. The state is a union of people, forming a single, permanent and independent whole. In him the idea of human society reaches its highest development. The opposite elements of common life, law and morality, which in the previous unions, in civil society and the church are expressed in a one-sided form and are reduced to the highest unity, mutually defining each other: in legal formations, common aims are realized, dominating over private ones which gives them moral significance [16, p.192]. The direct aim of the state is the harmonious arrangement of social life. This common aim is divided into as many separate aims as there are separate elements in the state, because each element, developing, has its own inherent purpose. In B.M. Chicherin, the main aims of the state are the establishment of security, the definition and protection of freedom and human rights, and the exercise of moral order. Also, the aim of the state is a combination of order and freedom. As the state is the union which reigns over all, this combination is the supreme realization of truth. This is his idea, which is the inner aim of development. This is the common good and therefore the state is the highest realization of the idea of good. At the same time, it is also the highest realization of freedom. But in public life moral demands are combined with material interests so far as they concern the whole union. The totality of those and others is the public good, which is the highest and ultimate aim of the state, containing all the others [17, p.10–15]. Despite the fact that there was even a classification of the aims of the state with a logical distribution, which are based on liberal values, it is the definition of aims and their classification that are predominantly philosophical in nature.

M.M. Korkunov, who is considered one of the founders of the domestic state law, in his famous work "Russian State Law" operates with such concepts as the aims and tasks of the state. He notes that the tasks of the state as well as the boundaries of the state, are determined by the coercive nature of the state system. So usually the question of the tasks of the state is raised, but it is solved differently by different political theories [18, p.52]. Having analyzed the works of well-known legal scholars of different times M.M. Korkunov comes to the conclusion that the question of "aims or tasks" of the state is interpreted in modern (late 19th century) theory of state in general briefly and formally, which was explained by the formal nature of the theory of state. At the same time, he notes that the broad tasks of state activity are not the subject of wishes alone, but all these tasks are actually carried out by states, and the dispute is not about whether the state can perform all this, but only whether such a desired amount of state activity. And argues that the state is a powerful cultural force capable of serving the implementation of many diverse tasks [18, p.74].

From the point of view of our research two important observations can be made. Firstly, in the second half of the 19th century (the first edition of "Russian State Law" was published in 1892, this work had eight editions, including four after the death of M.M. Korkunov) such concepts as the aims and tasks of the state had the same meaning, and the category of "state functions" was not introduced into science. Secondly, it is the evolution of the state (despite the formal nature of science - according to the author) and as a consequence of the birth of fundamental legal science. Over the years, legal science has played an important role in state-building and constitutional processes in particular.

S.A. Kotlyarevsky in his famous work "Legal State and Foreign Policy", having deep historical analysis of legal and political thought, came to the conclusion that theory of state generally much "cooling" to the issue of state aims and her rather withdrawn place the treatises on politics, and that these aims "captures the spirit of the historical era and therefore extreme mediation" [19, p.14]. At the time of the publication of this scientific work in 1909, such a category as aims of state was already a relative quantity, relevant in a particular state (type of state), in a certain historical era. In the evolution of legal and political thought has been transformed target ideas of the state from a scientific point of view, and introducing such sci-

entific categories as "state tasks" and "state functions". S.A. Kotlyarevsky was one of the first who introduced such a category as "state functions" into the domestic legal science. He noted that "ensuring external security is among the indisputable state functions, which were recognized in the most diverse and opposite assessments of the natural purpose of state activity" [19, p.236]. This statement was the beginning of Chapter 2 of this work entitled "Foreign Policy Problems of the Modern State". Thus, the author identifies the concept of functions and tasks of the state. At the same time, he notes that it is unlikely that the attempt to create a general classification of functions that would correspond to different aims, political, social and cultural, set by the state [19, p.14]. An important asset of S.A. Kotlyarevsky is that at the beginning of the 20th century it was clearly defined that the aims of the state, it is rather a political category, and the main activities of the state are already implemented through categories such as "state tasks" and "state functions".

The research of this issue is impossible (in our opinion) without the analysis of the works of the outstanding lawyer F.F. Kokoshkin, who operates with such concepts as the aims of the state, the tasks of the state and the functions of state power. F.F. Kokoshkin is a follower of the ideas of subjective and objective aims of the state. Research of the aims begins with statement of two questions – for what exist a state, and what aims put the state by "people who make it". In the first case, the question concerns the objective aim of the state, in the second – the subjective. In the rationalist (contractual) theory, which considers the state as the achievement of free and conscious human activity, the concepts of objective and subjective aims coincide: if the state is created by a free act of the reasonable will of people, it exists precisely for the purpose pursued by its creators, concluding the contract. But if we recognize that the state is not intentionally created, we must separate the question of the objective and subjective aim of the state [20, p.81].

The ideas of F.F. Kokoshkin are based on the public interest, while he notes that the public interest is "a certain riddle that has only approximately the right solution" [20, p.85], which accordingly reflected in the research of the aims and tasks of the state. The public interest is only the general concept under which the specific tasks of state activity are summed up, but this concept cannot in itself give a sufficiently clear idea of the specific tasks of state activity, since the state seeks to implement the coinciding, individual and

group aims in all spheres of human life. In many cases it attaches this task to the free activity of individuals and the free unions they form. Therefore, in determining the aims of the state, it is impossible to stop on the general concept of public interest, but it is necessary to find out which of the tasks that fit this concept are pursued by the state. Watching as for famous states, the aims of state activity, cannot be reduced to personal and class interests are recognized and in this sense, the state can reduce them to three groups or up to three primary aims – political, legal and cultural [20, p.85–56]. Thus, the system when the tasks of the state are derived from the general aim of the state, finds its confirmation in this research.

Another significant achievement of F.F. Koshkin was the introduction into the scientific space of such a category as the functions of state power, defining state power as a subjective right belonging to the state to obey subjects or citizens. This subjective right is exercised by the state in various forms, for example, in the form of issuing laws, addressing citizens with specific orders within the limits and on the basis of laws, the execution of court sentences. These separate forms of state power are called in legal science its functions. The functions of state power in this sense should not be confused with its tasks. As we saw above when considering the question of the aims of the state, from the general aim of the state there are separate tasks of state activity: protection of external security, protection of the right, care of economic welfare of the population, etc. But this classification of state activity with its internal content is absolutely independent of the considered classification of external legal forms of manifestation of state power [20, p.184–185].

During analyzing these statements, it can be concluded that the two categories "aims of the state" and "tasks of the state" have a logical and inextricable relationship, because the tasks of the state correspond to the aims and are based on the public interest. Aims also remain largely an abstract category, but are reflected in public life through the implementation of tasks. With regard to functions, the author deduces such a category as "functions of state power", which are based on the theory of separation of powers, but are not identified and are not reduced to three functions (legislative, executive, judicial), but much broader categories. In turn, in forms of realization of functions of the state power, it is possible to see a basis of future theories about state functions, with division into internal and external.

The establishment of the category "state functions" in the domestic legal science

In the Soviet Union era, the legal doctrine was based on the Marxist-Leninist principle, influenced the theory of the state and directly on the doctrine of the aims, tasks and functions of the state. Because of this the problem of the state and its influence on public relations became acute political in nature and was often used to characterize the socio-political structure of society. V.I. Lenin's thesis that "the state is by no means inert, it always acts, and acts very vigorously, always actively and never passively", in fact determined the formation of the theory of functions of the state in domestic science. The category "state functions" was first used in the research of active, managerial properties of the state, in the analysis of its social role. However, the integral, relatively independent theory and methodology of the classics were not [21, p.8]. In the works of K. Marx, F. Engels, V. Lenin, the concept of "function" in relation to the state is usually used in a broad sense to identify its general social purpose. In other words, in these works, it does not mean any particular kind of implementation of state power, and state activity as a whole, characterizing the state as an organization of class domination [22, p.141].

The modern concept and classification of the functions of the state were formed and firmly established in the domestic theory of state and law in the 60-70s years of the 20th century. Despite some not very significant differences in approaches to the definition of the concept of state functions, their content, in general, the views of almost all authors coincided [23, p.41]. It was during this period, in our opinion, that the category of "state functions" was formed in legal science, which logically follows from the "chain" of aims–tasks–functions, where functions are a means of realizing aims and tasks. It is also worth noting that this system remains relevant today in the Ukrainian scientific space.

Having passed a long historical way, aims of state remained an abstract category and only transformed into a political category, as a result of which the concept of "politically-legal aim" was even introduced as an ideally assumed model reflecting the state of social life to which the state aspires by reforming the relations, phenomena and processes that exist in the present. It forms the basis of long-term policy and determines the basic directions of improvement of legislation [24, p.31].

On the basis of the aims or one general aim, the tasks of the state are formed, which more

specifically express its essence and purpose. We have already mentioned, for example, the Constitution of the USSR (1977), in the preamble of which the supreme aim of this Soviet Union state is "the building of a classless communist society in which there will be public, communist self-government". And further the list of tasks is given directly: creation of material and technical base of communism, improvement of socialist general relations and their transformation into communist, education of the person of communist society, increase of material and cultural standard of living of workers, ensuring safety of the country, assistance to strengthening of the world and development of international cooperation [11, p.5]. Despite the ideological nature, this is a very qualitative example, relevant for our research. After all, scientific achievements have been implemented in practice and enshrined not only at the legislative but also at the constitutional level. Here we can see how one general aim of the state generates a number of tasks that should ensure its achievement.

As a consequence, the research of the correlation of tasks and functions comes to the fore, in comparison, for example, with the beginning of the 20th century. In the scientific community was established almost the only idea of the relationship between the tasks and functions of the state. The essence and social purpose of any state is manifested in its tasks and main functions. The tasks of the state are those questions to which the ruling class aspires. Functions of the state are the main directions of activity of the state on implementation of the tasks set before it [25, p.65].

The definition of the functions of the state, provided by A.I. Denisov and V.E. Guliyev, is worthy of attention, according to which the function of the state is its activity, which differs in the subject-political composition [26, p.80]. Thus, it is seen that there is a close relationship between the functions and aims of the state, despite the political nature. The tasks and functions of the state are correlated and closely interrelated, but do not coincide categories. They cannot be contrasted or identified. It is not necessary to mix the state functions with the principles of its formation and activity [27, p.63]. In particular, a clear correlation between the tasks and functions of the state was provided to the government. E.I. Temnov among which the tasks determine the very existence (implementation) of functions; arise before their implementation; are objective in relation to the function; determine the content of functions; affect the forms and methods of implementation of functions.

No such task can be solved without the functions of the state: same function can solve a number of tasks of the state, and vice versa; function is a more specific concept, because certain ways of state influence depend on economic and political needs of society, stage of development of the state, external and internal situation, correlation of political forces, national, ethical, religious and other features, etc. [28, p.173].

With the help of functions, it is possible to determine the nature of the state's activities, the correctness of its choice of priorities, the level of its organization and efficiency. It should be emphasized that in the modern legal literature, the definition of the functions of the state is proposed not only as directions of its activity, but also as a mechanism of state influence on social processes. And this is natural, because performing certain functions in certain spheres of public life, the state, together with the necessary reforms, legal regulation of public relations affects the state of social processes. The implementation of specific functions can both stabilize the conditions of development of society and strengthen its crisis state [29, p.62–63].

Conclusions

In our opinion, the main results of the research are:

1. "State functions" is the basic scientific category of the theory of state and law, its formation in legal science through the evolution of legal, political and philosophical thought. Study the main activities of the state (state functions) is only possible in combination with other categories such as aims and tasks of the state, conceptualize which caused the formation of the scientific category of "state functions".

2. The establishment and transformation of scientific views coincides with historical epochs, which corresponded to the realities characteristic of a certain historical period. The aims of the state, responding to the real social situation, remained a philosophical category, since they did not find their practical implementation, which was explained by the low development of legal science, and law was not the main regulator of public relations.

3. The revolutionary period in the development of the doctrine of the functions of the state was the Modern Period, characterized by the formation of constitutionalism and was associated with European legal schools. In addition to the emergence of new categories, such as the tasks and functions of the state, scientists of the Modern

Period have been improved philosophical, abstract doctrine of the aims of the state and laid the scientific foundations of a democratic, liberal, legal state.

4. In the research of the state functions, the works of domestic legal scholars of the late 19th and early 20th centuries were of great importance, in which entire states were finally formed as a political category, which is reflected in the tasks, and must be implemented through functions.

5. As of today, the aims and tasks have become correlated and express the social purpose

of the state, which has found its consolidation at the constitutional level. The functions of the state, having a correlation with the tasks, ensure the fulfillment of its social purpose.

Competing interests

The author of the article reports about the absence of any conflict of interest.

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SOCIAL-ECONOMIC FACTORS IN THE PREDICTIVE ESTIMATION OF CRIMES IN UKRAINE

(ABSTRACT, KEY WORDS)

Problem statement. The development of new forms of crime, as well as modern methods of its research, leads to the formation of fundamentally new approaches to the knowledge of the relationship between criminological indicators and predictors of crime. In the structure of crime, such interdependencies represent the most probable object of study, where the structure, level, intensity, and quality of crime are affected by a large number of identified and uncertain factors. A number of indicators are considered that affect the number of reported crimes, with the highest focus on macroeconomic indicators. First of all: the number of unemployed; the average monthly salary; consumer price index; the volume of industrial products sold; retail trade turnover; industrial production index; natural population decline. **The purpose** and the objectives of the study are: 1) conducting a correlation analysis between the relative quantitative indicator of crime and the relative indicators of economic development of the regions of Ukraine; 2) conducting a regression analysis and constructing a regression model of the relationship between individual socioeconomic indicators and the state of crime. The solution to these problems is to apply the author's approach to modeling the relationship between the crime rate and the relative indicators of economic development of the region, as well as to create a regression model of the prediction of the crime rate depending on the factors determined by the researcher and development factors. **Methods.** The research method is General scientific dialectical, statistic methods. **The result** of the study is the construction of an informative predictive model of crime, which allows quantifying the impact on crime by individual socio-economic factors. **Conclusions.** Construction of regression models and assessment of their quality showed that the most accurate equation is the dependence of the crime rate on retail turnover (per 10 thousand population) and on the number of unemployed (UAH per 1 person). On the basis of the basic variant of the projection, the principal possibility of forecasting the number of registered crimes per 10 thousand population by introducing into the model quantitative indicators of the economic development of the region, namely the number of unemployed and retail trade (in relative terms) is proved. The global tendencies of the dependence of crime on macroeconomic factors and technological development are analyzed. The practical significance of the obtained results for the development of programs for forecasting and minimizing the impact of future trends and patterns of crime are outlined.

Key words: *macroeconomic factors; relative indicators; regression models; forecasting the number of crimes; criminological and mathematical methods; the impact of technology development*

Problem statement

The development of new forms of crime, as well as modern methods of its research, has led to the formation of fundamentally new approaches to the knowledge of the relationship between criminological indicators and predictors of crime.

In the structure of crime, such interdependencies represent the most probable object of study, where the structure, level, intensity and quality of crime are affected by a large number of identified and uncertain factors. Factors in criminology are understood as factors of influence, predictors, de-

terminants, etc., that is, those aspects of influence on crime that operate in different directions without the possibility of specifying what that influence is: causal (which inevitably entails consequences) or influence conditions (which implements a temporary coincidence of all kinds of circumstances of a situational nature, which by themselves do not have the content of a specific negative premise).

Thus, according to the results of our research [1], the following three levels of factors are mainly influenced by the reliability of estimating and predicting crime rates:

– social, economic, political. These factors are general in nature and unrelated to a specific type of crime, but they have an impact on all processes occurring in society and the level of crime in general;

– the territory of the crime, the physical characteristics of the object, the temporal factors (above all, the external conditions of the crime, which, unlike the causes, are temporary), material conditions, and more. These factors are local in nature and related to the specificities of a particular place and region;

– personal, directly related to the person of the perpetrator and the victim.

However, it is the action of the macroeconomic indicators of these factors that has a comprehensive and demonstrable impact on various types of crime. These are such as individual influence on the formation of criminal motivation; the overall impact on the structure of crime and on the level of crime of selfish and selfish and violent direction; general and individual impact on the nature and results of crime prevention and resocialization and others.

Of particular importance are socio-economic factors of influence. For example, in the study of the determinants of regional crime that cause quantitative and qualitative changes in regional crime in Ukraine, A.M. Babenko calls the presence of aggregate resource and natural-resource potential in the regions, organizational and managerial miscalculations, negative consequences of economic transformations, factors of size and location of settlements, number and structure of population of the region, fertility, marriage and divorce, mortality, level of urbanization, migration [2, p.251–282]. V.M. Beschastnyj among the socio-economic factors, that have a pronounced connection with the criminal activity of the population, notes an increase in consumer prices (food, utilities, household goods, appliances, current housing maintenance, health care); decrease in real incomes of the population; rising unemployment; reducing the level of social protection of low-income groups [3, p.47-49].

In turn, O.M. Humin, on the impact of such a factor as unemployment, emphasizes that among the violent criminals there is a steady increase in the number of non-students who are not studying, are not engaged in work or other socially beneficial activities, although they have objective opportunities for this. This affects the formation of the motivational sphere of the offender [4, p.140]. O.O. Belousova notes that such a factor as the instability

of the economy also causes a significant influence on the strengthening of the positions of criminal formations in the regions (83% of the polled experts) [5, p.25].

According to a study by Alves L.G. Ribeiro H. V., Lenzi E. K., Mendes R. S. (2013) on the link between homicides and eleven factors in Brazilian cities, gross domestic product per capita, income levels, and the criminal age of the male population have a positive correlation with homicide; while child labor, the elderly population, the female population, illiteracy, poor living conditions, unemployment have a negative correlation with homicides [6].

Kelly M. (2000) on the link between economic inequality and crime for urban areas in the United States has demonstrated that socially disadvantaged people have committed the most violent crimes, and the most deprived members of society living in areas with significant social inequality face great pressure and incentives to commit crimes. This is what leads to their criminalization [7]. For Hojman D.E. (2004), inequality, unemployment, and crime in Latin American cities, taking into account the diversity of cities, are factors that influence poverty and inequality as causes of crime [8].

In general, the link between crime and various influences such as demographics [6] is demonstrated by Alves L.G. Ribeiro H.V., Lenzi E.K., Mendes R.S. (2013); economics [7; 9; 10] – Kelly M. (2000), Cotte Poveda A. (2012) and Lauritsen J.L., Rezey M.L., Heimer K. (2014) and unemployment [8; 11; 12] – study by Hojman D.E. (2004, 2002) and Levitt S.D. (2001). Therefore, the purpose of the article is to describe an informative predictive model of crime, which quantitatively characterizes the impact on crime of certain socio-economic factors. His scientific novelty is to model the relationship between crime rates and relative indicators of economic development in the region, as well as to create a regression model for predicting crime rates depending on the factors of relative economic indicators of the region's development. The objectives of the article are: analysis of crime statistics in the regions and dynamics of indicators of regional economic development; establishment of correlation between the relative quantitative index of crime and the relative indexes of economic development of the regions of Ukraine; constructing a regression model of the relationship between individual socio-economic indicators and the state of crime; outlining the world trends and main directions of further research.

Analysis of regional statistics and correlation between crime rate and economic development indicators

There are three main approaches to estimating crime rates: revenue, cost and comparability. At the same time, the crime rate is estimated on the basis of the moral-psychological personality traits of the offender, and indicators of the economic develop-

ment of the territory in which the crime is committed are often disregarded.

Tables 1 and 2 provide statistics on crime in the regions and the dynamics of regional economic development indicators as of 2018. Due to the lack of reliable data, since 2014, official state statistics do not contain statistical data on the Autonomous Republic of Crimea and Sevastopol.

Table 1 – Indicators of economic development of Ukrainian regions in 2018¹

Regions of Ukraine	Number of unemployed (thousand people)	Average monthly salary of the employee (UAH)	Consumer price index (%)	Sales volume of industrial products (UAH million)	Retail trade turnover (UAH million)	Industrial production index (%)	Natural movement of the population (decrease) (persons)
Vinnitsia Oblast	20,8	7672	109,0	69878,9	25264,5	101,2	10368
Volyn Oblast	7,8	7187	109,9	27398,6	16322,7	102,3	1949
Dnipropetrovsk	25,7	8743	109,2	435789,1	85085,4	102,3	24198
Zhytomyr Oblast	14,3	7259	109,1	40176,0	23376,7	97,3	8450
Zakarpattia Oblast	4,6	7902	112,2	21543,8	21921,8	104,6	952
Zaporizhia Oblast	22,3	8573	109,2	192905,8	38486,2	103,2	13685
Ivano-Frankivsk	8,1	7480	109,1	65011,4	21922,1	110,0	4114
Kyiv Oblast	12,3	8909	110,0	102345,2	65600,7	100,4	12078
Kirovohrad Oblast	15,6	7101	109,0	26750,1	16844,1	101,7	7538
Lviv Oblast	13,4	7893	110,1	90707,4	57552,0	101,4	8167
Mykolaiv Oblast	16,4	7980	109,4	51655,5	22369,4	102,6	7210
Odessa Oblast	16,6	7871	109,3	52490,7	69047,4	91,8	8920
Poltava Oblast	20,3	8232	109,3	168177,1	30932,0	101,4	12028
Rivne Oblast	12,0	7279	109,3	33553,3	17237,0	95,3	751
Sumy Oblast	15,5	7223	109,7	43767,6	19457,9	110,4	9707
Ternopil Oblast	9,6	6848	109,7	19670,6	13022,6	98,3	5780
Kharkiv Oblast	22,0	7528	111,2	169449,9	72132,3	101,9	20165
Kherson Oblast	11,2	6930	109,5	25645,7	21763,9	99,8	6204
Khmelnyskyi Oblast	12,9	7199	109,2	39543,4	20551,0	95,2	7974
Cherkasy Oblast	17,8	7375	109,7	63388,1	22532,7	101,9	10404
Chernivtsi Oblast	5,9	6805	108,7	13578,1	15151,8	105,5	2132
Chernihiv Oblast	11,8	6904	109,6	31687,9	18088,2	98,7	11152
Kyiv	8,6	13270	108,8	167980,6	176964,7	97,8	2790
Donetsk Oblast	10,7	9444	111,2	228893,5	22652,2	102,3	17745
Luhansk Oblast	8,2	7245	109,3	20748,5	8176,9	102,3	9316

¹ Compiled by the author on the basis of [13, p.25–27; 14–16].

Table 2 – Indicators of crime rate and structure, as well as population in regions of Ukraine in 2018²

Regions of Ukraine	Number of reported criminal offenses	Number of serious and especially serious crimes	The number of crimes committed while intoxicated	Number of crimes committed by persons who have previously committed crimes	Number of persons found to have committed crimes	The size of the population in the region
Vinnitsia Oblast	12589	4700	596	1839	4277	1561811
Volyn Oblast	9296	3576	399	1293	2446	1035867
Dnipropetrovsk Oblast	45652	17871	611	9605	12586	3209075
Zhytomyr Oblast	14178	5303	340	1425	4125	1221469
Zakarpattia Oblast	11006	4423	366	1171	3157	1257139
Zaporizhia Oblast	26607	9444	793	5207	6869	1707288
Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast	7386	2758	247	477	2281	1373705
Kyiv Oblast	20109	9396	384	2035	5580	1767172
Kirovohrad Oblast	15415	7206	363	2003	3194	946621
Lviv Oblast	25764	9036	471	3282	5844	2523116
Mykolaiv Oblast	19146	6534	442	2118	4223	1131984
Odessa Oblast	33038	14332	328	1711	5346	2380512
Poltava Oblast	21363	6591	686	4971	4847	1401694
Rivne Oblast	10273	3659	254	1454	2946	1157822
Sumy Oblast	11872	3839	243	2516	3870	1082317
Ternopil Oblast	7063	2240	63	442	2467	1046287
Kharkiv Oblast	36353	14130	1193	7429	7908	2678133
Kherson Oblast	16032	5790	319	3988	4170	1038691
Khmelnitskyi Oblast	11172	3458	341	1610	3526	1265781
Cherkasy Oblast	15559	6132	291	1100	2931	1207583
Chernivtsi Oblast	7725	2323	173	765	1949	904646
Chernihiv Oblast	14203	4403	501	1557	2917	1007224
Kyiv	60037	23390	142	2803	8204	2949558
Donetsk Oblast	20953	7537	-	-	-	4175471
Luhansk Oblast	10358	4262	492	2077	3677	2153216

² Based on [15; 17].

Table 3 presents the relative indicators of economic development of Ukrainian regions and crime rates in 2018.

Table 3 – Relative indicators of economic development of Ukrainian regions and crime rates in 2018³

Regions of Ukraine	Number of unemployed (persons per 10 thousand population)	Volume of industrial products sold (UAH per 1 person)	Retail trade turnover (UAH per 1 person)	Natural movement of population (persons) (decrease) (in%)	Number of reported criminal offenses (per 10 thousand population) - crime rate
Vinnitsia Oblast	133,18	44742,2	16176,4	0,66	80,6
Volyn Oblast	75,30	26449,9	15757,5	0,19	89,7
Dnipropetrovsk Oblast	80,09	135799,0	26514,0	0,75	142,3
Zhytomyr Oblast	117,07	32891,5	19138,2	0,69	116,1
Zakarpattia Oblast	36,59	17137,2	17437,8	0,08	87,5
Zaporizhia Oblast	130,62	112989,6	22542,3	0,80	155,8
Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast	58,96	47325,6	15958,4	0,30	53,8
Kyiv Oblast	69,60	57914,7	37121,9	0,68	113,8
Kirovohrad Oblast	164,80	28258,5	17793,9	0,80	162,8
Lviv Oblast	53,11	35950,5	22809,9	0,32	102,1
Mykolaiv Oblast	144,88	45632,7	19761,2	0,64	169,1
Odessa Oblast	69,73	22050,2	29005,3	0,37	138,8
Poltava Oblast	144,82	119981,3	22067,6	0,86	152,4
Rivne Oblast	103,64	28979,7	14887,4	0,06	88,7
Sumy Oblast	143,21	40438,8	17978,0	0,90	109,7
Ternopil Oblast	91,75	18800,4	12446,5	0,55	67,5
Kharkiv Oblast	82,15	63271,7	26933,8	0,75	135,7
Kherson Oblast	107,83	24690,4	20953,2	0,60	154,3
Khmelnitskyi Oblast	101,91	31240,3	16235,8	0,63	88,3
Cherkasy Oblast	147,40	52491,7	18659,3	0,86	128,8
Chernivtsi Oblast	65,22	15009,3	16748,9	0,24	85,4
Chernihiv Oblast	117,15	31460,6	17958,5	1,11	141,0
Kyiv	29,16	56951,1	59997,0	0,09	203,5
Donetsk Oblast	25,63	54818,6	5425,1	0,42	50,2
Luhansk Oblast	38,02	9636,1	3797,5	0,43	48,1

For the correlation analysis between crime and economic development of the region from tables 1 and 3, we select *the relative indicators of economic development of the regions and the number of reported criminal offenses per 10 thousand populations* (Y) – crimes. The factors of economic development are the following:

1) the number of unemployed per 10 thousand

population of the region (X1) – persons;

2) average monthly salary of an employee in the region (X2) – UAH;

3) consumer price index in the region (X3) – %;

4) volume of industrial products sold per person (X4) – UAH;

5) retail trade turnover per person (X5) – UAH;

6) industrial production index (X6) – %;

7) natural decrease of the region's population (X7) – %.

The results of the correlation analysis are presented in table 4.

³ Calculated on the basis of tables 1, 2.

Table 4 - Correlation coefficients between crime rates per 10,000 population (Y) and regional economic development indicators (X1–X7)

Variable	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	X6	X7	Y
X1	1,000000							
X2	-0,407647	1,000000						
X3	-0,376302	-0,009986	1,000000					
X4	0,207349	0,392448	-0,093435	1,000000				
X5	-0,147058	0,752570	-0,170053	0,306939	1,000000			
X6	0,016347	-0,111572	0,171944	0,153740	-0,238936	1,000000		
X7	0,706983	-0,270204	-0,146201	0,397475	-0,095720	0,081389	1,000000	
Y	0,404453	0,417271	-0,255541	0,408920	0,702189	-0,231757	0,338184	1,000000

From their analysis it can be established that:

- there is a strong correlation between the number of unemployed (X1) and the natural decrease of the population of the region (X7) – the correlation coefficient is 0.71, between the average monthly wage of the worker (X2) and the turnover of retail trade (X5) – 0.75, between the number crimes per 10 thousand population (Y) and retail trade turnover (X5) – 0.70;

- there is a weak correlation between the number of unemployed (X1) and the average monthly wage of an employee (X2) – (-0.41), the number of crimes per 10 thousand population (Y) and the number of unemployed (X1) – 0.40, the number of registered crimes (Y) and the average monthly wage (X2) – 0.42, the number of crimes (Y) and the volume of industrial production (X4) – 0.41, the volume of industrial production (X4) and the natural decrease in the population of the region (X7) – 0.40;

- there is practically no correlation between the number of reported crimes (Y) and the consumer price index (X3), the industrial production index (X6), and the natural decrease in the region's population (X7).

At the stage of constructing the regression model, the economic factors that have the greatest impact on crime are selected. Due to the fact that many factors make the model cumbersome, inconvenient to use and complicate the study of the impact of individual predictors, it is necessary to include only a rational set of factors in the final version of the regression model.

The factor exclusion method we use is that highly correlated factors are excluded from the regression. They are selected using the Cheddock scale. Significance criteria – even correlation coefficient: 0 to 0.3 – no relationship; 0.3 to 0.5 – weak link; 0.5 to 0.7 – moderate communication; 0.7 to 1.0 – strong connection [18].

Factors X1, X2, X4, X5 are closely related to the dependent variable Y, which is why they form the basis of the crime prediction model. Since factors X2 and X5 are highly correlated (0.75), only one of them should be included in the regression model.

This is the factor X5 because of its greater correlation with the dependent variable (Y).

Regression model of crime intensity depending on given factors

For calculations, we have chosen a linear function because of its simplicity of interpretation and the smallest prediction error. Thus, the equation for the prediction of the crime rate is:

$$Y = A_0 + A_1 * X_1 + A_4 * X_4 + A_5 * X_5,$$

where Y is the value of the function (the number of reported crimes per 10 thousand population is the crime rate);

A₀ is a free member of the regression equation;

A₁, A₄, A₅ are regression coefficients;

X₁ – number of unemployed per 10 thousand population;

X₄ – volume of industrial products sold per person;

X₅ – retail trade turnover per 1 person.

The use of multivariate analysis to calculate the number of reported crimes gives more accurate results than the pair correlation, so in most cases such analysis is more prioritized. The multiple correlation method allows you to calculate the number of reported crimes as a whole, and the paired correlation method is better used to calculate individual changes. For a detailed study of the relationship and the estimation of the accuracy of the forecast, one can further build one-factor models:

$$Y = A_0 + A_1 * X_1;$$

$$Y = A_0 + A_4 * X_4;$$

$$Y = A_0 + A_5 * X_5.$$

The initial data for constructing the regression models are presented in Table 5. The following is an assessment of the adequacy of the constructed regression equations and verification of the possibility of describing the relationship between the response function and the predictors of the linear model:

$$Y = A_0 + A_1 * X_1 + A_4 * X_4 + A_5 * X_5.$$

The check used the STATISTICA Multiple Regression module (StatSoft Inc., USA).

Table 5 - Baseline data for constructing a regression model⁴

Regions of Ukraine	Number of unemployed (persons per 10 thousand population) (X1)	Industrial output (UAH per person) (X4)	Retail trade turnover (UAH per 1 person) (X5)	The crime rate (per 10 thousand population) (Y)
Vinnitsia Oblast	133,18	44742,2	16176,4	80,6
Volyn Oblast	75,30	26449,9	15757,5	89,7
Dnipropetrovsk Oblast	80,09	135799,0	26514,0	142,3
Zhytomyr Oblast	117,07	32891,5	19138,2	116,1
Zakarpattia Oblast	36,59	17137,2	17437,8	87,5
Zaporizhia Oblast	130,62	112989,6	22542,3	155,8
Ivano-Frankivsk Oblast	58,96	47325,6	15958,4	53,8
Kyiv Oblast	69,60	57914,7	37121,9	113,8
Kirovohrad Oblast	164,80	28258,5	17793,9	162,8
Lviv Oblast	53,11	35950,5	22809,9	102,1
Mykolaiv Oblast	144,88	45632,7	19761,2	169,1
Odessa Oblast	69,73	22050,2	29005,3	138,8
Poltava Oblast	144,82	119981,3	22067,6	152,4
Rivne Oblast	103,64	28979,7	14887,4	88,7
Sumy Oblast	143,21	40438,8	17978,0	109,7
Ternopil Oblast	91,75	18800,4	12446,5	67,5
Kharkiv Oblast	82,15	63271,7	26933,8	135,7
Kherson Oblast	107,83	24690,4	20953,2	154,3
Khmelnitskyi Oblast	101,91	31240,3	16235,8	88,3
Cherkasy Oblast	147,40	52491,7	18659,3	128,8
Chernivtsi Oblast	65,22	15009,3	16748,9	85,4
Chernihiv Oblast	117,15	31460,6	17958,5	141,0
Kyiv	29,16	56951,1	59997,0	203,5
Donetsk Oblast	25,63	54818,6	5425,1	50,2
Luhansk Oblast	38,02	9636,1	3797,5	48,1

The results of the information processing program are evaluation indicators and significant standardized regression coefficients:

Dependent: [The crime rate](#).
 Multiple R = [0,86979447](#) (multiple correlation coefficient);
 F = [34,18241](#), df = [2,22](#), p = [0,000000](#) (F-criterion value, number of degrees of freedom, and significance level p) - used as a general F-criterion to test the hypothesis of predictor dependence and response;
 R² = [0,75654243](#) (coefficient of determination);
 No. of cases: [25](#) (the number of observations on which the regression model is constructed);
 adjusted R² = [0,73440992](#) (adjusted coefficient of determination);
 Standard error of estimate: [21,036395848](#) (standard error of estimation). These statistics are a measure of the

scattering of the observed values relative to the regression line;

Intercept: [5,359584660](#) (estimation of free regression term A₀);
 Std.Error: [14,44986](#) (standard free member evaluation error A₀);
 t(22) = [0,37091](#), p = [0,7143](#) (t-criterion value and significance level p) to test the hypothesis that zero is free of A₀;
 retail trade turnover b* = [0,779](#);
 the number of unemployed b* = [0,519](#).

The variable "Volume of industrial products sold" was defined by the program as not being a significant predictor. It follows that the relationship between response and predictors is strong (R² > 0.75); constructed linear regression adequately describes the relationship between response and predictors, the free term being statistically significant. In the table 6 shows the model performance.

⁴ Based on Tables 1-3.

Table 6 - Model: regression results

N=25	Beta	Std. Err. of Beta	B	Std.Err. of B	t(22)	p-level
Intercept			5,359585	14,44986	0,370909	0,714253
Retail trade turnover	0,778503	0,106353	0,002979	0,00041	7,320022	0,000000
Number of unemployed	0,518938	0,106353	0,514737	0,10549	4,879415	0,000071

Table 6 contains standardized (Beta) and nonstandardized (B) regression coefficients (weights), their standard errors, and significance levels. Beta coefficients are estimated from standardized data having a sample mean of 0 and a standard deviation of 1. This compares the contributions of each predictor to the response prediction. Yes, the dependent variable Y (the crime rate) contributes more to variable X5 (Retail trade turnover) and less to X1 (Unemployed). The fact that the coefficients for the variables are not negative numbers means that with the increase in retail trade turnover and the number of unemployed, the number of registered crimes increases.

The regression equation can be used to predict

the values of the response - the number of crimes reported per 10,000 population by the values of the predictors: retail turnover and the number of unemployed.

For example, if you enter the value "retail trade turnover (UAH per 1 person)" – 40,000, and "number of unemployed (persons per 10 thousand population)" – 150, then the predicted (number of registered crimes (crime rate) – 201,7470 per 10 thousand population with 95% confidence interval (178,0996; 225,3943).

One of the conditions for the correct application of regression analysis is compliance of the law of distribution of residues with the normal law, the graph of which is presented in the diagram.

Diagram - Schedule of distribution of residues

The graph shows that due to the small number of observations (25), the distribution of residues does not fully correspond to the normal law.

By regression analysis, we can determine that the linear model looks like:

$$Y \text{ (The crime rate)} = 5.3596 + 0.514737 * X1 \text{ (Unemployed)} + 0.002979 * X5 \text{ (Retail trade turnover)}$$

Summand "Retail trade turnover" with a coefficient of 0.002979 from this particular model can be

excluded because of the statistical insignificance of the coefficient. That is, the hypothesis of equality of zero is correct.

Note that this model will be sufficiently accurate, provided that the independent variables (predictors) lie within the limits specified by the data table. Outside these limits, the model may be unreliable.

Outlining the world trends and main directions of further research within the framework of criminological modeling and forecasting

The practical application of this model is optimal within the framework of the general concept, the basic scheme of which [19, p.32] is given by Canadian criminologists led by Stephen Sneider (2007). According to these criminologists, the influence of two factors is quite significant: macroeconomic indicators (for example: economic development, unemployment, consumer spending) and demographic factors (the number of men at the age most prone to crime) [19, p.8]. In the case of Ukraine, modeling should also take into account the level of population migration. Another important factor is the development of technology in the country and the age structure of the population.

This shows that in countries with a large proportion of the young population there is a steady increase in crime and in countries with an "aging nation" – the crime rate tends to decrease. Time series models of the relationship between the potentially criminally active population and the crime rate tend to indicate that both property and violent crime rates correlate significantly with changes in population structure.

Although the impact of economic development on crime rates has been the subject of much debate, there is no doubt that such an impact is most noticeable when analyzing self-serving crime. Thus, in periods of economic growth in the country decreases the number of selfish encroachments, and in periods of regression and decline their number is steadily increasing. However, economic growth in countries with a significant shadow economy and significant corruption has no negative correlation with unemployment. Therefore, conclusions about the level of selfish and corrupt crime that are relevant to countries with a traditionally normalized economy do not always work for countries whose economies are corrupt.

On the other hand, there may be a situation where the growth of the shadow economy leads to a gradual enrichment of part of the population, thus creating the conditions for committing crimes against property. In this case, we are dealing with a macroeconomic indicator - consumer spending.

Absence of correlation or a positive correlation between the unemployment rate and the level of consumer spending can indicate problems of economic development, which in turn inevitably lead to an increase in the real level of selfish and property crimes. It should be borne in mind that official statistics can conceal this fact because of the same corruption issues in law enforcement agencies and lack of control over the registration discipline.

The macroeconomic indicator of government spending per capita has a negative correlation with the level of self-serving crimes in the country. That is, with the reduction of spending from the budgets of all levels on social programs, education, medicine, etc., the number of selfish crimes increases. This conclusion is valid for countries with any economic development.

Regarding the impact of technological development of the state on crime, there is an opinion on the distribution of such influence in three directions: a) technological progress provides criminals with new tools for committing traditional crimes (for example: fraud, theft, money laundering and counterfeiting); b) technology itself becomes the target of criminal offenses (such as telecommunication theft, services and the spread of viruses); c) new technologies will be used to prevent or deter criminal acts [19, p.10].

Today, the most likely criminological prognosis for the future is the rapid impact on technology development in Ukraine of self-serving crime. Any automation programs in the country should be securely protected, and professionals should in a specific way minimize the risks involved in the introduction of new technological developments at the state level, with due consideration for the consequences of possible crimes.

Finally, there is another important factor in influencing crime. This is the criminal justice system itself. In Ukraine, it is constantly undergoing reform, but it does not produce stable positive results. The following are necessary steps in this direction: increasing the funding of law enforcement, judicial and penitentiary agencies; introduction of the latest technologies; improving the efficiency of correctional facilities; increasing the role of public and private individuals in crime prevention.

Predicting crime is one of the most controversial topics in criminal justice today. Studies have argued that this analytical approach is based on statistics, where most forecasting models are informational, and the use of large data sets, as noted by Liv Nadine (2019), places a primary emphasis on correlation rather than causality [20, p.5]. The main

problem with the use of crime prediction technologies is the display in the official statistics of police reactions to the facts of criminal behavior, and nowhere in the world can they claim full objectivity in displaying real crime rates.

Conclusions

1. An assessment of the dependence of registered crime indicators on the economic development of the territory has shown a strong correlation between crime rates and the number of unemployed, as well as between crime rates and retail trade turnover.

2. Using regression models and assessing their quality confirmed that the most accurate is the equation of the crime rate ratio on retail trade turnover (per 10 thousand population) and the number of unemployed (UAH per 1 person). On the basis of the basic variant of the projection, the principal possibility of forecasting the number of registered crimes per 10 thousand population by introducing into the model quantitative indicators of the economic development of the region, namely the

number of unemployed and retail trade (in relative terms) is proved.

3. Prospective directions of the research are construction of other estimation models of quantitative dependence of crime indicators (or individual crimes) on various factors (step, logarithmic, polynomial, exponential functions) and inclusion in the model of crime level prediction, along with indicators of economic development of the region, characterizing social, political, legislative, environmental and other changes in society and the state.

Competing interests

The text of this article is made by the author himself. The author declares that there is no conflict of interest or infringement of the intellectual property rights of any third parties.

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**SOME ASPECTS OF HUMAN DEFENSE
IN THE WORK OF EXPRESSED REPRESENTATIVES
OF PHILOSOPHICAL OPINION OF NEW HOURS**

(ABSTRACT, KEY WORDS)

The article analyzes the understanding of the concept of "dignity" in the writings of such prominent representatives of the philosophical and legal thought of modern times as J. Locke, B. Spinoza, T. Hobbes, I. Kant, G.V.F. Hegel, L. Feuerbach, J.J. Russo. According to the author, this will contribute to a deeper and more complete understanding of the concept of "dignity", "human rights and freedoms", given that the evolution of the understanding of the category "dignity" is closely intertwined with the history of the struggle against injustice and oppression of man, for freedom and equality. The author put forward the following tasks: to reveal the modern understanding of the notion of "dignity", to analyze the peculiarities of the views of the eminent thinkers of the seventeenth and eighteenth centuries, to show how elementary moral ideas of dignity were formed and the basic legal principles were introduced in English, American, and French law. In the process of solving the tasks, the author came to the conclusion that respect for human dignity, that is, the idea of the value of an individual from ancient times was and is the subject of attention of philosophers, lawyers, its uniqueness is the basis of the modern philosophy of human rights, and the dynamics of human rights is a consequence of specific historical conditions that correct the significance and relevance of those goods reproduced by the respective rights. Understanding human dignity is unequal in different historical epochs in different nations. An analysis of the views of the thinkers of the New Times has shown that the notion of dignity is identified with the value of a man; it is associated with a person's awareness of the fact that it possesses significant moral and intellectual qualities for it. At the same time, dignity depends on the position of man in society, the state of society, the ability to ensure the practical establishment of inalienable human rights, the recognition of the self-worth of the individual. The scientific novelty of the work consists of a comprehensive study of the views of eminent thinkers of the XVII–XVIII centuries, the essence and content of human dignity.

Key words: morality; person; recognition of self-worth of the person; inalienable human rights

Problem statement

One of the most important features of a modern democratic society is respect for the rights and dignity of the individual. The latter has the character of relations based on the norms of morality and law, the principles of freedom and mutual responsibility between the state, society and the individual, between different individuals and social groups. Civil society is the bearer of relevant values. The state, represented by its bodies and officials, undertakes obligations for their implementation, ensuring the protection of the dignity of its citizens.

Ukraine proclaimed itself in The Constitution of Ukraine (1996) as a legal state (Article 1), enshrined in it the provision that a person, his life and

health, honor and dignity, inviolability and security are recognized in Ukraine as the highest social value (article 3). Enshrining the right to respect the dignity of a person in legislation requires the definition of the term "dignity", understanding its essence and content.

The term "human dignity" comes from the Latin (dignus – "valuable"). The general ethical value of human dignity is reflected by modern researchers in the following definitions: "Human dignity - the concept of moral consciousness, expressing the idea of the value of each person as a moral person, as well as the category of ethics, which means a special moral attitude of a person to himself and the attitude to it from society, which recognizes the

"value of personality" [1, p.81–82]; "human dignity is an expression of his personal value" [2, p.1206].

V.A. Bachinin defines dignity as an ethical and natural-law category, which means the value of the human person, recognized both by the person himself and his social environment. He believes that it is natural law philosophy that reduces the legal formula of human dignity to universal ethical maxims and religious "absolutes" [3, p.283]. The authors of the textbook on ethics define human dignity as an objective, social and moral value of the person, as well as the need and proper assessment of the person's moral value [4, p.98]. Representatives of legal science, defining dignity, argue that human dignity is recognized and protected by law and the rule of law value, which forms one of the foundations of a constitutionally organized society [5, p.475]. G.D. Bandzeladze in his work "On the Concept of Human Dignity" defines human dignity as an essential feature and quality that distinguish a person from other beings and, at the same time, do not just distinguish, but constitute her sense of superiority, superiority on a certain scale of values and according to certain criteria of progress [6, p.11].

Among foreign studies, it is necessary to note the works of German scientists, because for the first time it was in the Basic Law for the Federal Republic of Germany that the inviolability of human dignity was recognized as a leading constitutional principle: "Human dignity shall be inviolable. To respect and protect it shall be the duty of all state authority" (part 1 of article 1 of the Basic Law of Germany) [7, p.580]. Such authors as G. Durich, A. Blankenagel, E. Bloch, V. Maihofer, V. Pirot, B. Schlink, R. Behrendt, R. Spaeman and others developed the theoretical concept of human dignity.

German scientists believe that the content of the concept of dignity changes over time and depends on the culture of the society in which it develops. German legal science refuses to define dignity as once and for all established. A. Blankenagel rightly notes, that we should not fill the content of human dignity with our modern ideas about it for future generations, for another society, the modern formula can only be the source material through the variability of its cultural content [8, p.388].

Indeed, the norm on human dignity was conceived by the creators of the Constitution, first of all, as a protection against cruel degrading treatment by the state. It was about the physical integrity of a person. Today we are talking about respect

and the protection of personal identity and psychological integrity of a person. So modern researchers in the field of human rights V. Pieroth and V. Schlink determined that human dignity is violated when the treatment of public authority with a person, proposed by law, calls into question its value as a person. A free person, its value and autonomy must be respected and protected by the state. It is forbidden to treat it as a means even for the sake of the best intentions. This is contrary to the dignity of the human person [9, p.89]. This position is confirmed and developed by W. Maihofer, which states that respect for human dignity is expressed in the guarantee by the state of a person's freedom of moral self-determination. According to position W. Maihofer, human dignity is the foundation of the rule of law, which should guarantee a person respect and protection of his dignity (inviolability) [10]. It should be noted that the inviolability of human dignity in the legal system of Germany acts simultaneously as a "basic norm of legislation" and the most important constitutional principle, which is revealed in the rights and freedoms enshrined in the Basic Law [11, p.85].

Therefore, the characteristic of dignity as a value of the person is uniform for all offered definitions, both ethical, and legal. In this regard, questions arise: what determines this value? What is the recognition of human value by society?

Hence, the purpose of the article is to analyze the concept of "dignity" in the works of prominent representatives of philosophical and legal thought of New Hours. In our opinion, this will contribute to a deeper and fuller modern understanding of the concept of "dignity", "human rights and freedoms", given that the evolution of the understanding of the category of "dignity" is very closely intertwined with the history of the struggle against disenfranchisement and oppression of human for freedom and equality. The relationship between the individual and the state in recent centuries is the main problem of political and legal thought, because without taking into account these relationships is not possible to establish order in society.

The scientific novelty of the research consists in a comprehensive study of the views of prominent thinkers of the XVII–XVIII centuries, the essence and content of human dignity. The aim of the article is to reveal the modern understanding of the concept of "dignity"; to analyze the features of the views of prominent thinkers of the XVII–XVIII centuries; to show how elementary moral ideas about dignity were formed and the basic legal principles in English, American and French law.

Formation of elementary moral ideas about dignity

Human dignity in all its aspects has a deep social meaning. Man is essentially determined by the whole system of social relations, the product and subject of social relations. Therefore, human rights are objectively, naturally and historically formed in society as its social opportunities, which meet partially or completely its needs in real life [12, p.104]. As noted F.M. Rudinsky, the idea of human dignity means the recognition of human as the highest, incomparable value, which implies the recognition of its subject of freedom, equality, ownership of its rights and obligations of human and citizen [13, p.229].

The idea of the dignity of the individual began to form in the early stages of human society. In the conditions of the primitive communal system, elementary moral ideas about the dignity of the person were formed. The ideas of the value of the individual and his freedom were first comprehensively developed in the philosophical, ethical and political-legal doctrines of Ancient Greece and Rome. One of the peaks of ancient Greek humanism was the doctrine of Protagoras, who proclaimed: "Human is the measure of all things". Defending the idea of human equality, he believed that such virtues as wisdom, virtue, the possibility of participation in public life, available to all people. Praising human, recognizing his absolute value, Protagoras was much ahead of his time, became a harbinger of humanistic ideas of thinkers of the New Time [13, p.231]. At the same time, the social value of the person, his freedom in the ancient world was of a class character. Slaves were completely excluded from the sphere of freedom and, according to the prevailing slave-owning morality, could not be carriers of dignity.

The ancient Roman legislation reflected the laws on the freedom of the person, formed in the ancient world, but it was already considered as an instrument of the speaking slave (*instrumentum vocale*). Human quality recognized slaves Stoics (Zeno, Seneca), for which had significance only domestic, freedom spiritual, not associated with any socio-political status rights.

Feudalism, which replaced the slave system, became a new stage in the development of human personality. However, class barriers associated with the feudal hierarchy, entrenched social inequality, limited the creative possibilities of human. The principle of equality of people before God, put forward in the early Christian doctrine, became a form of affirmation of human dignity. Supported by

Christianity, the ancient idea of the likeness of human to God ("in the image and likeness of God") offered personality, although at the same time the legend of the creation of Adam and Eve is designed to justify the humiliation of human before the Almighty Creator. The dogma of the fall, in our opinion, is incompatible with the idea of human dignity, is the basis of the preaching of Christian self-death of the flesh, asceticism, monasticism, self-destruction of the person. And the very practice of the Catholic and other Christian churches (the activities of the inquisition, the persecution of heretics) for centuries prevented the assertion of human dignity.

The basis of the formulation of the modern concept of "dignity" was, in our opinion, primarily Protestant ethics with its individualism and rationalism. It should be noted that it is in the era of the reformation that the content of the concept of human dignity is deepening. And it is connected with formation of representations about the person as the subject of personal freedom and the carrier of inalienable subjective rights.

The religious experience of "communion with God" in Protestantism was based on personal experience and personal spiritual experience, in contrast to the mediated process of knowledge of God in other faiths and religions. The rationality of labor activity proceeded from Martin Luther's interpretation of the New Testament, according to which the importance of secular professional work and religious retribution for it increased enormously. In other words, the value of human activity on earth has increased. The Protestant socio-cultural tradition created the "social ethics" of European culture, and this had a constitutive significance for it [14, p.99–100]. The era of the reformation became a new stage in the development of the idea of human dignity [12, p.42]. Prominent thinkers XVI–XVII centuries saw the social value of human in his creative activity, in its desire to strengthen its power over nature (D. Bruno, F. Bacon, D. Locke). The progressive philosophers of New Time were convinced of the power of the human mind. And this is an important aspect of the formation of the idea of human dignity.

Features of views of outstanding thinkers of XVII–XVIII centuries

It should be noted that in New Times, the content of the concept of human dignity, associated with the formation of ideas about the person as a subject of personal freedom and the carrier of inalienable rights [13, p.232]. The peculiarity of the ethical, political and legal teachings of the XVII–XVIII centuries

is that they considered the social value of the individual from the standpoint of the school of natural law.

The development of the problem of the dignity of the citizen as a subject of personal freedom is central to the political doctrine of J. Locke. He wrote that "The liberty of man in society is that it is subject to no other legislative power than that which is established by consent in the state, where there are no laws, there is no freedom" [15, p.16]. J. Locke theoretically developed such principles of bourgeois constitutionalism (respect for the right of private property, sovereignty, parliamentary rule, division of power, legality, inalienable rights of persons), which formed the "empirical system of democracy" and the philosophy of American constitutionalism [16, p.34]. The doctrine of J. Locke found its embodiment in the constitution and these principles became the basis for legal interpretation [17, p.100–101]. J. Locke defended the right to freedom, but allowed a partial restriction on the benefit of the state. At the same time, the philosopher denied the total renunciation of the individuals natural rights. The right to life, property, dignity of a person, equality, a person does not alienate anyone under any circumstances [18, p.271–272].

Thus, the interests of the person become the center of all state activity by J. Locke. In this regard, the question of the dignity of the citizen receives a new interpretation. Personal dignity becomes an attribute of private property, just as in the Middle Ages it was an attribute of origin and class.

The political teachings of J. Locke had a huge impact on the subsequent development of political ideology. Especially widespread was the theory of natural inalienable human rights, which was used by T. Jefferson and other theorists of the American revolution and subsequently included in the Declaration of the Rights of Man and of the Citizen (1789) [19, p.189–190].

B. Spinoza paid much attention to the dignity of the individual as the most important aspect of freedom in his teaching. Such high moral qualities as honesty, gratitude, courage, generosity, inherent only in free people. The wisdom of a free man, as he claimed, "consists of thinking not about death, but about life" [20, p.576]. This is an optimistic and life-affirming position was by anti-clerical orientation. The main idea of his "theological-political treatise" was that the destruction of freedom in the state would mean the destruction of the very tranquility of the state [12, p.47].

B. Spinoza has the merit of advancing the idea of human dignity, regardless of his nationality. He

wrote that "In regard to intelligence and sincere virtue, no nation differs from another" [21, p.62].

During the New Time, various aspects of the problem of human honor and dignity were elaborated in detail. Thus, T. Hobbes analyzes the ratio of such moral categories as power, value, dignity, and respect for human.

He compared the value of human with the value of things and considered it as a price, which is as much as can be given for the use of his power [22, p.95]. Dignity by T. Hobbes is the social value of human that is the price that gives it the state. Consequently, the social dignity of man is identified with the civil.

I. Kant defined dignity as an absolute value, possessing which a person makes other people respect themselves, at the same time comparing themselves with them, evaluating themselves. According to I. Kant "The person represents all dignity of mankind, to dispose of itself as means for any purpose means to humiliate dignity of mankind in the person to whom the person for preservation was entrusted" [23, p.360].

"The respect that I feel for others, or such that others may demand of me is as a consequence, the recognition of dignity in another person that is dignity which has neither a price nor an equivalent that can be exchanged for an object of honor" [23, p.404] wrote I. Kant. According to the philosopher, above compassion and love (which are worthy of respect) is respect for human dignity.

The presence of dignity (absolute value) gives a person the right to be respected by others; the right to self-esteem and at the same time imposes on her the duty to respect the dignity of others. Unlike his predecessors I. Kant put forward the thesis that society cannot limit a person's individualism, his personal interest. Human dignity is based on autonomy. The state is obliged not to interfere in this sphere of life of the person as long as it violates the law.

Merit of I. Kant is creating an ethical concept of human dignity, according to which its implementation is impossible without the provision of human rights and freedoms, while the person is not a means to an end. This is what provided the rationale for the idea of human rights and its further development in the theory of the rule of law.

In the philosophical system of G. V. F. Hegel, the individual is considered as an element of the general, organic whole, the moment of moral totality. Considering the state as the procession of God in the world, the reality of the moral idea he defends the thesis of the primitiveness of the state in

relation to the person. At the same time, the philosopher made a significant contribution to the development of the doctrine of human dignity. Especially important in this respect was Hegel's concept of freedom as known necessity.

G. V. F. Hegel as a supporter of a moderate constitutional monarchy advocated the granting of elementary rights to citizens (although he recognized the natural and necessary hierarchical structure of society and condemned the "rabble", that is the poor).

G. V. F. Hegel wrote about the need to elevate the dignity of human, the recognition of his ability to be free, in his opinion it will put man on a par with everything spiritual [24, p.224]. That is the philosopher saw the dignity of human in its freedom. He saw the benefit of self-government of citizens in the state, in particular, in the fact that it provides them with a sense of self-esteem [25, p.85]. Despite all the contradictions inherent in the philosophy of G. V. F. Hegel, his belief in the triumph of reason confirmed the idea of a high social value of the person.

This idea was further developed in the works of L. Feuerbach, which in the conditions of semi-feudal Germany of the first half of the XIX century from the position of materialism and atheism fought against religion, idealism for social progress, education, for the freedom of the person. Having put forward the anthropological concept of human, the philosopher considered it as a part of nature, a set of certain physiological and moral qualities.

The dignity of human by L. Feuerbach is that he acts as a carrier of freedom. In revealing its contents, he on the one side denied Jean-Jacques Rousseau arguing that human is not born free, because freedom is the result of education on the basis of appropriate innate gifts [26, p.645]. On the other side, he defended the eudemonistic concept and rejecting the Kant's ethics which declared that freedom without happiness is an empty and devoid of content word [27, p.580]. L. Feuerbach sought to fill the freedom of the individual with political content. "The policy of the state and the Church is in blatant contradiction with the good, freedom and the very essence of human" [27, p.595]. He owned the well-known for today thesis: "Human does not exist for the sake of the state, but the state for the sake of human" [28, p.436]. He called unlimited monarchy an immoral state. It should be noted that L. Feuerbach highly extolled man. "Human to human is God - is the highest practical principle, and this is the turning point of world history" [29, p.308–309]. He regarded love to human as the fundamen-

tal principle of morality. In our opinion it is impossible not to recognize the high humanity of this position.

The connection between rights and freedoms and the recognition of human dignity has been considered by other philosophers. For example, J.J. Rousseau believed that "Essence who is capable of experiencing, acting, consults exclusively with his passions and turns to reason only to correct the absurdities that they make her do" [30, p.455]. He saw the social value of the individual in being the subject of freedom. "Human is born free" J.J. Rousseau asserted in his "The Social Contract". To renounce freedom is to renounce one's human dignity, the rights of human nature, even its duties [30, p.152, 471].

The establishment of the basic legal principles in English, American and French law

English lawyer and statesman A. V. Dicey in the XIX century introduced into scientific circulation the concept of "Rule of Law" [31, p.49].

The term introduced by A.V. Dicey became widespread in England and America and began to mean that certain fundamental principles of justice cannot be legally affected even by the highest authority. Human dignity and human rights do not arise by the will of the state, but by the essence of human nature. A. V. Dicey found the source of these basic legal principles in the fundamental laws of the land, in the English Constitution, as well as in case law. In the English tradition, even Parliament though superior to other public institutions is constitutionally subject to the basic principles of justice embodied in the historical traditions of the English people. These principles and historical traditions gradually took the place of the main values of law and politics: freedom of discussion and public assembly, as well as the inviolable rights of the subject - the right to guarantees against unlawful deprivation of life, liberty or property, to a fair trial, equality before the law regardless of position in society. "Habeas corpus act" (1679) contained the principle of inviolability of the person, the presumption of innocence [32, p.26–38] and "Petition of Right" (1628) laid on the king's duties to protect subjects from the arbitrariness of the royal administration [33, p.6]. If the king contributes to the violation of peace and liberties, that is, violates the principle of good and justice, approved by "Magna Carta Libertatum" (1215) - "It is possible to use the right to revolt by the community of the whole earth" [33, p.373].

Bourgeois revolutions and the establishment of capitalist society were important factors in the development of human personality and its rights. The liquidation of the old feudal system, the estates of

the realm distribution, and the abolition of the personal dependence of the worker on the owner of the means of production had great progressive importance. At the end of XVIII - the beginning of XIX centuries honor and dignity become the object of constitutional protection. In the United States Declaration of Independence (1776) bourgeois-democratic principles of freedom and equality of people were proclaimed, that is essential elements of concept of value of the human person [31, p.182–186]. In the legislation of The Bourgeois Revolution in France the concept of honor of the citizen is associated with the ideas of protecting the motherland, with hatred for political tyranny (Constitution of 1793) [31, p.120–126].

The legal documents of the United States of America and France have become a kind of standard, a model for the legislative consolidation of primarily physical and personal ("civil") and political human rights (they were later called the rights of the first generation). Similar and other human rights and their guarantees were already defined in the legislation of many other countries at that time. Ukraine did not remain on the sidelines of these processes.

Conclusions

Consequently, respect to the dignity of the individual in ethics is axiological category, which is directly related to the categories of value and evaluation, is formed in the individual and public consciousness and is determined through the philosophical category of "value"; dignity acts as an objective property of the individual and is characterized by spiritual, physical and moral qualities. Human unlike other living essences is able to know himself, evaluate his own "I" and thereby determine his place in society. That is, the uniqueness of a person is that it is able to realize and comprehend its own value.

The analysis of the views of thinkers of New Time shows that the concept of dignity is identified with the value of a person; it is associated with the realization of the fact that a person has significant

moral and intellectual qualities. At the same time, dignity depends on the position of a person in society, the state of society, his ability to ensure the practical assertion of inalienable human rights, the recognition of the self-worth of the individual.

The political and social transformations taking place in our country today require fundamentally new approaches to addressing the issue of respect for the dignity of the individual. The main legal guarantee of the right to respect for human dignity is that the establishment of restrictions on the rights and freedoms of a person must be consistent with the values of the rule of law, which are protected by the constitution and laws. All restrictions must take into account the necessary balance of interests of the person, society and the state. Such restrictions can be established only at the level of the law. This requires that the provisions of the law be clearly defined. The ambiguity of the legal content of the law and the possibility of its free interpretation and application is not consistent with the duty of the state to protect the dignity of the individual.

We believe that the constitutional establishment of the right to dignity is not sufficient to protect it. The criminal procedure code of Ukraine contains a general provision that enshrines the requirement of respect for the individual in criminal proceedings, to all its participants, regardless of what procedural function they perform, at all its stages.

But, requires addressing the issue of the normative definition of the object of the right to dignity. The first step towards solving this problem should be a normative definition of the concept of "dignity", which, unfortunately, does not exist in Ukrainian legislation today.

Competing interests

The author of the article reports about the absence of any conflict of interest.

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ADMINISTRATIVE AND LEGAL PRINCIPLES OF ACTIVITY OF SPORTS FEDERATIONS IN UKRAINE: ANALYSIS OF CURRENT PROBLEMS

(ABSTRACT, KEY WORDS)

It is shown that the mechanism of administrative-legal regulation of activity of sports federations in Ukraine is determined by the state's sports policy, the role of local self-government in this process, as well as public associations and organizations of sports and sports orientation. The purpose of the article is to deepen understanding of the peculiarities of the legal principles of the specified regulation of social relations in this area and the development of proposals for improving its efficiency. It is determined that the basic principle in the field of physical culture and sports in the state is the Law of Ukraine "On Physical Culture and Sports" of 1993, which defines the general legal, organizational, social and economic foundations of activity in the field of physical culture and sports and regulates social relations in creating conditions for the development of physical culture and sports. Among the subjects of physical culture and sports occupy special place sports federations. The differences in the understanding of sports federations in Ukraine and abroad, where foreign sports federations, a system of sports clubs, and the activities of foreign sports federations is really aimed at obtaining sporting results and meeting the sports needs of its members. It is recommended in Ukraine to focus on the third type of organization and activities of sports federations of France, the priority of which is the equation for all sports and multidisciplinary activities among different categories of the population. Recommended for sports federations among the unique, recognized only in Ukraine, types of physical culture and sports to receive international recognition before granting them the status of national ones. Provided suggestions to eliminate unacceptable duplication of sports federations and the observance by all sports federations of the task of developing sports as the main statutory requirements, as well as the restoration of the general principle of the existence and organization of sport – free access to what is defined for its subject. It is recommended to consider the conditions for the sports federation to acquire a certain (for example, national, all-Ukrainian) status as an element of its state accreditation. It is concluded that the results only confirm the urgent need for a further revision of some of the fundamental principles of the sports federations' activity and to improve the current legal framework, which will contribute to the unequivocal improvement of the sphere of physical culture and sports in Ukraine.

Key words: administrative and legal bases; activities; sports federations; physical culture and sport

Problem statement

The specificity of the field of physical culture and sport as a social and cultural system of the state today requires a comprehensive management of it. The currently engaged mechanism of administrative and legal regulation of the industry, on the one hand, allows a clearer distribution and

coordination of management efforts to develop domestic sport, and on the other hand, has led to the emergence of negative signs of increasing administrative and functional isolation and the formation of narrow-minded interests.

The mechanism of the administrative-legal regulation of activity of the sports federations rep-

resenting certain kinds of sports existing in Ukraine, and the list of which is confirmed by the central body of executive power in the sphere of physical culture and sports, is defined by a sports policy of the state, a role in this process of bodies of local government, and also public associations and the organizations of a physical culture and sports orientation. Therefore *the analysis of modern problems of administrative-legal bases of activity of sports federations in Ukraine*, is chosen as the purpose of the article, allows to deepen understanding, including, the mechanism and features of the legal bases of the specified regulation of public relations in the given sphere and to develop offers on the increase of its efficiency.

Moreover, as of today, research in this field of science has already received support and interest from both scientists and practitioners. It, for example, works Lischuk S.V. "Mechanisms of the state regulation of physical culture and sports of Ukraine" [1], Zhurba M.A. "Public management in the field of physical culture and sports" [2], Dutchak M.V. "Theoretical and methodological bases of formation of system of sports for all in Ukraine" [3], Morgun V.P. "Administrative and legal status of sports federations in Ukraine" [4] and others.

Mission and types of sports federations

It is necessary to notice that base in the field of physical culture and sports in the country is the Law of Ukraine "About physical culture and sports" from 24.12.1993 No. 3809–XII [5] by which the general legal, organizational, social and economic bases of activity in the field of physical culture and sports are defined and public relations in the creation of conditions for development of physical culture and sports are regulated. Among the subjects of physical culture and sport, such as sports clubs, schools of higher sportsmanship, etc., a special place is occupied by sports federations, which, in particular, may be the founders of Olympic training centers. In article 20 of the specified Law *sports federations (associations, unions, unions, etc.) are understood as "public organizations of a physical culture and sports orientation which main objectives are: maintenance of interests of members of corresponding sports federations in sphere of sports, including assistance in protection of their social, economic, creative, age, national-cultural and other interests; assistance to development of corresponding kind (kinds) of sports by participation in working out and performance of corresponding programs; attraction of members of corresponding sports federations in the field of sports"*.

As of today, according to some obsolete data of Ukrainian Wikipedia [6], in Ukraine there are federations of aviation sport, boxing, badminton, basketball, biathlon, bicycle sport, judo, etc., and together with the all-Ukrainian status, some of them, for example, the Federation of Athletics of Lviv region, has a clearly defined regional status. Approximately the same situation with sports federations is observed in Azerbaijan (https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Категорія:Спортивні_федерації_Азербайджану) Russia (https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Категорія:Спортивні_федерації_Росії), Croatia (https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Категорія:Спортивні_федерації_Хорватії) and others.

It is quite clear, that any sports federation in a certain kind of physical culture and sports should be focused, first of all, on development of this kind of physical culture and sports, and it should be reflected both in its name, and in the charter. And the Azerbaijan Badminton Federation itself (Azerbaijan: Azərbaycan Badminton Federasiyası) is an organization engaged in badminton competitions on the territory of Azerbaijan (https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Федерація_бадмінтону_Азербайджану); All-Russian Athletics Federation is a "Russian sports organization engaged in the development and popularization of athletics in Russia and the organization and conduct of national competitions in this sport" (https://uk.wikipedia.org/wiki/Всеросійська_федерація_легкої_атлетики).

At the same time, regarding the concept of federation, without considering its well-known meaning in the theory of state and law, it is a union of separate societies and organizations – for example, a federation of national associations, sports federation.

Concerning *Sports Federation*, it is, according to foreign standards, *the existing system of sports clubs, including for a certain category of citizens*, for example, for persons with sight impairment, the mentally retarded, deaf people and so on. Probably, it is not superfluous to say that in Ukraine, in our opinion, there are not enough official sports federations for people with disabilities and certain physical disabilities. And this is despite the fact that the site (<http://scu.org.ua/federacii-neolimpijskogo-sporty-ukrainu-28.html>) of the Sports Committee of Ukraine directly indicates the existence of 47 All-Ukrainian federations, which is somehow not enough for 164 there are listed existing sports.

In general, it is necessary to notice that in the Register of recognized sports in Ukraine [7] for today it is designated 56 Olympic sports, 110 non-Olympic kinds of sports, and 51 kinds of sports of

invalids with lesions of the musculoskeletal system, lacks of sight, hearing and mental and physical development (*sports, but not sports federations!* – *Aut.*) – about what, actually, it was spoken earlier.

Differences in understanding of sports federations in Ukraine and abroad

Today we see certain differences in the understanding of sports federations in Ukraine and abroad. First, foreign sports federations, it is, as already noted, *a system of sports clubs*, and their number in the early XXI century, only in the EU countries was 700 thousand, which were engaged in about 40 million people [8, p.182]. Secondly, the activities of foreign sports federations are actually aimed *at obtaining sports results and meeting the sports needs of their members*. In Ukraine it is, conditionally speaking, a kind of "business", though officially unprofitable, organizations. Moreover, they even allow their representatives to be engaged in activities not at all sports orientation [9]. Although here, as well as abroad, sports federations are not disgusted with mere sponsorship [10] and the search for additional government funding. It is possible that domestic sport will someday receive a rule of law, according to which "sports clubs belonging to the state (municipal) or public form of ownership are non-profit and private clubs are commercial".

In the same France, however, *"a sports federation is an alliance of sports associations (governed by the 1901 Act) whose purpose is to bring together affiliated sports groups and licensed players in order to organize sports, particularly through competition. Federations can be accredited by the Ministry: the law recognizes that they have a public service mission. Some of them have been delegated to establish sports discipline practices. They sign a permanent contract with the state, which allows the organisation of competitions"* [11]. There are several types of federations – Single-sport federations, Multisport federations and "Peer" federations. In our opinion, *Ukraine*, for activation of attraction of the wide masses of the population to physical culture and sports, *it is necessary to be guided by the third type of the organisation and activity of sports federations of France*, which priority is equalisation on all kinds of sports and versatile actions among different categories of the population (that, actually, is the key to understanding of appointment of sports federations. – *Aut.*).

In Ukraine sports federations follow the accepted grouping by kinds of sports as Olympic, non-

Olympic and sports of disabled people, and are structured as national, all-Ukrainian and local.

In any case, for the federations recognized only in Ukraine, as follows from Part 8 of Art. 20 of the Law of Ukraine "On Physical Culture and Sport" from 24.12.1993 No. 3809–XII [5] as amended by the Law No. 2074–VIII of 25.05.2017, *the status of national sports federation is given only "in case of absence of corresponding international sports federation"* – that is, *the conflict in equality of the rights to reception of the status "national"* between traditional already internationally recognised national sports federations and federations unique, but recognised only in Ukraine is imposed. And this is despite the fact that the status of the national is predetermined only one sport federation in the relevant sport.

In this regard, our comments found support and the Main scientific and expert department of the Verkhovna Rada of Ukraine in the fact that "questions of recognition of national sports in Ukraine are already sufficiently regulated in the current legislation, in this regard, the proposals of the bill will only lead to the burden of the current version of the law" [5, p.2]. Besides, perhaps, without detracting from the importance and need for the emergence and development of unique, inherent only in Ukraine, types of physical culture and sports, nevertheless, *it would be necessary to get at least some international recognition*, and not to crown themselves with a national status at once. By the way, contrary to the present norm of the Law, the so called ordinary way of inclusion in the Register of recognized sports in Ukraine [7] in the status of national federations at one time quite successfully passed such non-Olympic sports based on national-cultural traditions, as Ukrainian Belt Wrestling (All-Ukrainian Federation of Traditional Wrestling), Ukrainian Hand-to-hand Combat "Spas" (All-Ukrainian Federation of Hand-to-hand Combat) and Horting (All-Ukrainian public organization Ukrainian Horting Federation).

Restricting people free access to sport in the activities of some sports federations

Again, analyzing the names of sports federations with the status of a national sports federation [12], one can see that there are very few "purely sports" federations in this list – so, out of 69 federations only 24 have the word "sports" in their name or derivatives of it. The same Law of Ukraine "About physical culture and sport" [5] defines sport as "activity of subjects of physical culture and sport, directed on revealing and uniform compari-

son of the achievements of people in physical, intellectual and other preparation by carrying out of sports competitions and corresponding preparation for them". At least, in our opinion, this definition exactly as a sports federation does not formally meet the same public association "All-Ukrainian Federation of Cynological Sports", where "sports competitions and appropriate preparation for them" are aimed at dogs, not "to identify and uniform comparison of the achievements of people in physical, intellectual and other preparedness. By the way, the public organization "Cynological Union of Ukraine" is registered in Ukraine at the same time, apparently, with similar in meaning statutory tasks.

Or, for example, to compare the All-Ukrainian public organization "Federation of the security guards of Ukraine", the sport for which is "all-round bodyguards", and the public organization called "All-Ukrainian Union of public organizations the "Federation of bodyguard of Ukraine". Obviously, the nonsense here is too narrow, purely professional composition of persons who can be members of such federation. Firstly, it limits the possibilities of free access directly to participation in such kind of sport, as "not bodyguards", and secondly, Public Association "All-Ukrainian Federation of Military and Sport All-rounds", registered as national much earlier, already has a task to develop such sport as "military and sport all-rounds", the unconditional part of which is "all-rounds of bodyguards" or "all-rounds on other professional features of united persons".

Conversely, a purely sporting one by the name of the All-Ukrainian public organization "Federation of Underwater Sports and Activities of Ukraine", in our opinion, requires the deletion of the words "underwater activities" from its name as not having an obvious connection with the legally defined notion of sport. Or, is there a significant difference between such sports federations with the status of national sports federations, such as the Public Association "Ukrainian Federation of Wakeboarding and Waterskiing" and All-Ukrainian public organization "Federation of Water Skiing and Wakeboarding", registered by the same order of the State Youth sport from 04.12.2012 No. 5038? Why in Ukraine absolutely does not work the principle that *"the possibility of two... sports federations, cultivating the same kind of sport, is excluded by the structure of sports federations, built by analogy with the structure of national cultural autonomies"* [13, p.156].

Therefore, today is an urgent need for a more critical attitude to the order of registration by the

Ministry of Youth and Sports of Ukraine of these or those sports federations – at least *eliminate unacceptable duplication and compliance with all sports federations of the task of developing sports as the main statutory requirements*. In addition, *violated and the general principle of the existence and organization of sport – free access to what is defined as its subject*: if it is, by example, sports tourism, or water skiing, or chess, etc., participation in it may not be limited to any professional or other features and requirements. Perhaps, the conditions for a sports federation to acquire a certain (for example, national, All-Ukrainian) status should even be considered as an element of its original state accreditation.

It should be noted that in Ukraine, along with sports federations registered and other organizations aimed at the development of sports - for example, the Physical Culture and Sports Society "Dynamo" of Ukraine (1990), the Association "National Sport and Health of Ukraine" (1991), All-Ukrainian Physical Culture and Sports Society "Kolos" agro-industrial complex of Ukraine (1991), All-Ukrainian public sports organization "Central sports club of the militia of Ukraine" (1998), which has not yet updated its name, Sports Student Union of Ukraine (2002), All-Ukrainian public sports organization "Association of Women's Football of Ukraine" (2010) and others, which, hopefully, and still successfully perform their statutory functions in relation to the development of sports. And by the way, as noted by A.N. Semerkina, "the most common types of public organizations in modern Ukraine are physical culture and sports (18 %)" [14].

Selective financing and perception of sports federations as problematic by the state program of physical culture and sports development

By the way, as earlier it was already mentioned about the *state financing of activity of organizations of sports direction*, then, for example, among such items of expenses of the State budget of Ukraine for 2017 [15], as "physical and sports training of pupils and students"; "financing of creation of objects of the Western rehabilitation-sports center and creation of the All-Ukrainian rehabilitation-restorative sports center of NKSIU"; "Ministry of youth and sports of Ukraine"; "development of sports of invalids and their physical culture-sports".

Unfortunately, last year's questions of the organization and activity of sports federations in Ukraine have not received due attention in such important legal act, as the State target social pro-

gram of development of physical training and sports for the period till 2020, accepted by the Decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of Ukraine from 01.03.2017 No. 115 [16], if not to pay attention to the small thesis present there about "increase of level of publicity and transparency of activity of the Ministry of Youth and Sports, *autonomy of sports federations*" as a component "the third, optimum". But there is much more misunderstanding here – why the Government considers the development of physical culture and sports for the period up to 2020 to be a "problem" by giving one of the thematic titles: "Ways and means of solving the problem". Or, as it is possible to describe with the State Program by years ahead the number of persons who *have received* (exactly so, "will not receive", but "have received"! – Author's note) monetary rewards, or "the number of athletes who *have received* assistance to solve social and domestic issues" – see Annex 3 to the Program.

Today the basic in activity of the majority of federations, as the public organizations of physical culture and sports orientation that allows them to work, is presence at them the certificate of registration of association of citizens and an extract from the Uniform state register of legal bodies and phys-

ical persons-entrepreneurs; the registered charter and the certificate or other document confirming membership of sports federation in corresponding international federation; presence of the certificate on development of corresponding kind (kinds) of sports on territories.

Conclusions

Now there is no question about complication or restriction of activity of sports federations or the organizations of a sports direction in Ukraine by some artificial frameworks – on the contrary, the state only promotes their development. At the same time, the results only confirm the urgent need for further revision of some basic principles of such activity and improvement of the current regulatory framework, which promotes the unconditional improvement of physical culture and sports in Ukraine.

Competing interests

There is no conflict of interest in the subject matter of the article.

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**TO UNDERSTANDING OF THE BURDEN OF PROOF
IN ANGLO-AMERICAN LAW**

The basic purpose of this article is to explicate understanding and verbal expression of the burden of proof in Anglo-American law. For this, the method of comparative analysis of few analogous fragments from different editions of Black's Law Dictionary is used. As a result, firstly, the set of concepts and corresponding terms by which the burden of proof is understood and expressed is found out. In a first approximation, omitting analogous ones, it is appropriate to restrict the subset of terms, on the one hand, by "(legal) truth", "belief", "burden of persuasion", "risk of nonpersuasion" and, on the other hand, "burden of production" or "burden of going forward with the evidence", "prima facie case", "order of proof". Secondly, understanding and expression of the burden of proof vary greatly depending on recognition of one or the other legal standard of proof. Thirdly, understanding of the burden of proof has evolved and is currently functioning in the following principal dimensions: legal, rhetorical, and logical. These ones complement dimensions of space and time that are natural for any human activity. Fourthly, it seems possible to extrapolate the conclusion about legal-rhetorical-logical multidimensionality of concept of the burden of proof to entire cluster of concepts (and terms) which grasps legal proof, including concept of proof beyond a reasonable doubt. Thus, any attempt to reduce definitions of elements of this cluster, in particular – of concept of proof beyond a reasonable doubt, to pure logical definitions will be unsuccessful in general case. The conclusion is that the multidimensionality of concept of proof beyond a reasonable doubt seems to be an actual source of well-known difficulty of unification of practical explanation and using of standard of proof beyond a reasonable doubt.

Key words: proof; legal proof; burden of proof; proof beyond a reasonable doubt; Anglo- American law; Black's Law Dictionary

Problem statement

Article 17 of the Code of Criminal Procedure of Ukraine 2012 includes idea of proof beyond a reasonable doubt, which is an essential innovation for our law. This idea, obviously, was borrowed from still quite distant for us – both literally and figuratively – Anglo-American law, where it gradually during about two hundred years took root in description of the due process¹. However, how to

understand and use it correctly under conditions of the Ukrainian law? And whether this "transplantation of an alien" does not entail some undesirable inconsistency or even a dangerous "reaction of rejection"? Any search for answers to these and related questions actualizes the need for preliminary in-depth study not only of the very idea of proof beyond a reasonable doubt but also of a set of concepts (and corresponding terms) related to this idea, especially in their natural context². This

¹ In Great Britain and the USA some mentions of proof beyond a reasonable doubt occurs at the end of the XVIII century. This legal phenomenon and the term calling it had become widely accepted from the second half of the XIX century. Standard of proof beyond a reasonable doubt have got the constitutional status in the USA since 1970 (see, e.g., (Kenney S. 1995 : 990–992)). Nevertheless, the appropriate concept is under intensive discussion until now. At the very end of the XX century on base of careful

analysis, Thomas V. Mulrine concluded: "No judicial system in any country in the world adequately defines the concept of 'innocent until proven guilty beyond a reasonable doubt.' Virtually no definition of this concept escapes criticism." (Mulrine T. V. 1997 : 225).

² During the recent few years, concept of proof beyond a reasonable doubt and some related to it have been stud-

need is reinforced by current widening of the domestic specialists field of practice: they are becoming increasingly involved in different litigation in jurisdictions of the USA, England, etc. Therefore, in order to succeed here, they must be well-versed in the original concepts and in the appropriate terminology.

Concept of proof beyond a reasonable doubt is a natural element of the set, or better to say cluster, with central concept of *legal proof*. A core of this cluster as well as a core of cluster of corresponding terms were found in my previous paper. The latter core includes, first of all, "truth", "proof" and "evidence", "to prove" and "to evidence", "degree of proof", "burden of proof", "standard of proof", "standard of proof beyond a reasonable doubt", "standard of proof by preponderance of the evidence", "standard of proof by clear and convincing evidence", "legality", "admissibility" as well as "belief", "conviction" and "to convince", "persuasion" and "to persuade" (Tiaglo O.V. 2018 : 24).

Term "burden of proof" seems quite important element of the cluster mentioned. Therefore, in this paper I have an intention to explicate this term in frame of the wider discussion of the burden of proof phenomenon in Anglo-American law. Black's Law Dictionary, the first edition of which was published in 1891 and the tenth in 2014, provides representative material for this type of research³. This dictionary is positioned as the most widely used and authoritative secondary legal resource in frame of the Anglo-American law today. However, it has not yet found proper analysis and discussion in Ukraine. This circumstance was the additional stimulus to write the article proposed.

Evolution and contemporary understanding of the burden of proof

Explanations regarding the burden of proof in the first and second edition of the Black's dictionary coincide by essence (cf.: (Black H.C. 1891 : 157-158) and (Black H.C. 1910 : 156)). Some difference is in the fact only that the second edition includes references to real cases that were the

ied in publications of Ukrainian and Russian researchers: see, for example, (Budylin S.L. 2014), (Stepanenko V.V. 2017), (Tiaglo A.V. 2018), (Tiaglo O.V. 2013, 2018).

³ Henry Campbell Black himself had prepared only the first edition and the second one entitled "A Law Dictionary" and published in 1910. The subsequent editions with traditional title "Black's Law Dictionary" were prepared by different groups of experts.

sources for these explanations.

"BURDEN OF PROOF. (Lat. *onus probandi*). In the law of evidence. The necessity or duty of affirmatively proving a fact or facts in dispute on an issue raised between the parties in a case. Willett v. Rich, 142 Mass. 356, 7 N. E. 776, 56 Am. Rep. 684...

The term 'burden of proof' is not to be confused with '*prima facie* case'. When the party upon whom the burden of proof rests has made out a *prima facie* case, this will, in general, suffice to shift the burden... Kendall v. Brownson, 47 N. H. 200... (Black H.C. 1910 : 156)⁴.

Even these initial explanations reveal a fundamental fact: concept of the burden of proof is important for understanding of not a mono-logical activity, to which, in principle, logical proof can be reduced but of a legal dispute between parties defending different, often completely incompatible positions⁵. It is significant, this goes beyond boundaries of, so to speak, logical dimension – above all, into legal dimension.

The third edition of the dictionary was published after the death of H. C. Black. Of the two paragraphs cited above, only the first was reproduced here practically literally, and the second one included important additions.

"The term 'burden of proof' is not to be confused with '*prima facie* case', Kendall v. Brownson, 47 N. H. 200... or with expressions referring to a similar

⁴ According to the Black's dictionary, the Latin expression "*prima facie*" means "at first sight", "as far as can be judged from the first disclosure", "presumably", etc. It is explained further, a litigating party "is said to have a *prima facie* case when the evidence in his favor is sufficiently strong for his opponent to be called on to answer it. A *prima facie* case, then, is one which is established by sufficient evidence, and can be overthrown only by rebutting evidence adduced on the other side..." (Black H.C. 1910 : 938)

⁵ In accordance with the classical Aristotle's explanation, "reasoning is an argument in which, certain things being laid down, something other than these necessarily comes about through them. (a) It is a 'demonstration', when the premisses from which the reasoning starts are true and primary, or are such that our knowledge of them has originally come through premisses which are primary and true: (b) reasoning, on the other hand, is 'dialectical', if it reasons from opinions that are generally accepted" (Aristotle 1975 : 4). Therefore, in accordance with Stagiriite, correct logical proof, or the demonstration, from true premisses draws with necessity (only one) true conclusion. To achieve this result, in principle, one reasonable individual is sufficient. Such standard of proof is understood as proof beyond *any* doubt, or the demonstration.

idea, such as the 'burden of evidence,' Hyer v. C. E. Holmes & Co., 12 Ga. App. 837, 79 S. E. 589, 60, or 'the burden of proceeding,' Mason v. Geist (Mo. App.) 263 S. W. 236, 237, or the burden of going forward with the evidence, First Nat. Bank v. Ford, 30 Wyo. 110, 216 P. 691, 694, 31 A. L. R. 1441.

It is frequently said, however, to have two different meanings: (1) the duty of producing evidence as the case progresses, and (2) the duty to establish the truth of the claim by preponderance of the evidence, and though the former may pass from party to party, the latter rests throughout upon the party asserting the affirmative of the issue. Sellers v. Kincaid, 303 Ill. 216, 135 N. E. 429, 433 ... Again 'burden of proof' is sometimes used to refer merely to the rule of practice fixing the order of proof, as distinguished from the 'preponderance of the evidence' meaning the weight of evidence. Welch v. Creech, 88 Wash. 429, 153 P. 355, 358, L. R. A. 1918A, 353 ... "(Black H.C. 1933 : 258)⁶.

The above fragment clearly divides the target aspect from the procedural aspect of the burden of proof. The aim of proof here is the truth, or true knowledge, and in this sense, legal proof is similar to logical. At the same time, this aim is achieved through the use of not the logical standard but the special legal standard of proof: preponderance of the evidence. In general, this standard does not guarantee the achievement of only indisputable truth. In other words, the "legal truth" established in this way really remains only more or less probable knowledge, not excluding the possibility of error and, therefore, legal objection. Finally, the procedural aspect of the burden of proof includes the order of proof according to some practical rule.

The fourth edition of the Black's dictionary was published for the first time in 1951, and in 1957 and 1968 were published its two reprints. As can be seen from the reprint of 1968, the dictionary entry "Burden of Proof" almost exactly reproduces the content of its analogue of 1933 (Black H.C. 1968 : 246). In contrast, the analysis of the 1979 fifth edition reveals significant changes alongside with some succession.

"Burden of proof. (Lat. *onus probandi.*) In the law of evidence, the necessity or duty of affirmatively proving a fact or facts in dispute on an issue

⁶ It is well known that for criminal cases Anglo-American law uses stronger standard of proof than proof by preponderance of the evidence. The fragment cited is valid, for instance, for some civil cases.

raised between the parties in a case. The obligation of a party to establish by evidence a requisite degree of belief concerning a fact in the mind of the trier of fact or the court.

Burden of proof is a term which describes two different concepts: first, the 'burden of persuasion', which under traditional view never shifts from one party to the other at any stage of the proceeding, and second, the 'burden of going forward with the evidence', which may shift back and forth between the parties as the trial progresses. Ambrose v. Wheatley, D.C.Del., 321 F. Supp. 1220, 1222" (Black H.C. 1979 : 178).

A comparison of these fragments with the analogous ones in the third and fourth editions finds significant changes. These relate, first of all, to aim of proof: now proof is aimed not to reach the truth but to establish in the minds of, above all, judges and jurors the requisite degree of belief in a fact or in a party's position in whole. The way to achieve such belief is a persuasion process that, in fact, is a matter not of logic but, if one remembers Aristotle again, of dialectics or, even more importantly, of rhetoric⁷. Of course, the persuasion can be based on the logical search for indisputable truth or on the operations with this truth. However, is this recognized as necessity in all real litigations between all real parties?

Further, basic explanations regarding specificity of implementation of the burden of proof depending on nature of any specific case and, accordingly, on standard of proof adopted in this case were proposed in the fifth edition's entry.

"The burden of proof may require a party to raise a reasonable doubt concerning the existence or nonexistence of a fact or that he establish the existence or nonexistence of a fact by a preponderance of the evidence, by clear and convincing proof, or by proof beyond a reasonable doubt. Except as otherwise provided by law, the burden of proof requires proof by a preponderance of the evidence. Calif. Evid. Code, § 115.

In a criminal case, all the elements of the crime must be proved by the government beyond a reasonable doubt. In re Winship, 397 U.S. 358, 90 S.Ct. 1068, 25 L.Ed.2d 368...

⁷ Rhetoric, in accord to Stagirite, discovers the possible speech means of persuasion in reference to any subject whatever. There are three kinds of such means, or proofs: "The first depends upon the moral character of the speaker, the second upon putting the hearer into a certain frame of mind, the third upon the speech itself, in so far as it proves or seems to prove" (Aristotle 1926 : 15-17).

'Burden of establishing' a fact means the burden of persuading the triers of fact that the existence of the fact is more probable than its non-existence. U.C.C. § 1-201(8)" (Black H.C. 1979 : 178).

According to the Black's dictionary, in Anglo-American law after the middle of XX century concept of the burden of proof and some related to it concepts, at least in part, had gone beyond the classical logical dimension. A crowding out or, possibly, partial replacement of their logical understanding with the rhetorical one is a contemporary law fact⁸. In this regard, the change in the aim of (legal) proof seems very indicative: *directly* requisite degree of belief of the jury and judge was recognized as such aim but not achievement or support of indisputable truth.

In the sixth edition of the dictionary, published in 1990, the entry of the burden of proof is reproduced with little or no change. In contrast, the next 1999 edition has profound transformations in both the form and content of the relevant material. In subsequent editions of 2004 and 2009, with the exception of purely informational and technical innovations, explanation of concept (and corresponding term) of the burden of proof reached some stability. One can understand it, given, in particular, the fact that Brian A. Garner, a well-known American specialist in legal lexicography, remained the editor-in-chief of the recent editions of the Black's dictionary. In this situation, I restrict myself to further consideration only of the relevant entry of the ninth edition.

"Burden of proof. (18 c.) 1. A party's duty to prove a disputed assertion or charge. The burden of proof includes both the *burden of persuasion* and the *burden of production*. – Also termed *onus probandi*. See SHIFRING OF THE BURDEN OF PROOF. 2. Loosely, BURDEN OF PERSUASION. [Cases: Evidence ⇄ 90.]" (Black H.C. 2009 : 223)⁹.

⁸ It seems necessary to point out that contemporary – informal – logic includes in its subject matter not only demonstrative but also non-demonstrative reasoning based both on "true and primary" premisses and on opinion, or probable premisses. In this sense, informal logic overcomes the Aristotelian division of logic and dialectics (see, e.g., (Tiaglo A.V. 2008 : 167-169)). Nevertheless, even this essential transformation does not allow to grasp the means of persuasion, which depend on the "moral character of the speaker" or the hearer's "certain frame of mind", within boundaries of logical dimension.

⁹ This article includes information about the period when expression "burden of proof" appeared in English: this is XVIII century. In addition, the West key number

Further this brief purely dictionary article was complemented and clarified by the fragment from contemporary university casebook.

"In the past the term 'burden of proof' has been used in two different senses. (1) The burden of going forward with the evidence. The party having this burden must introduce some evidence if he wishes to get a certain issue into the case. If he introduces enough evidence to require consideration of this issue, this burden has been met. (2) Burden of proof in the sense of carrying the risk of nonpersuasion. The one who has this burden stands to lose if his evidence fails to convince the jury or the judge in a nonjury trial. The present trend is to use the term 'burden of proof' only with this second meaning. Rollin M. Perkins & Ronald N. Boyce, *Criminal Law* 78 (3d ed. 1982)."

And once more addition here.

"The expression 'burden of proof' is tricky because it has been used by courts and writers to mean various things. Strictly speaking, burden of proof denotes the duty of establishing by a fair preponderance of the evidence the truth of the operative facts upon which the issue at hand is made to turn by substantive law. Burden of proof is sometimes used in a secondary sense to mean the burden of going forward with the evidence. In this sense it is sometimes said that a party has the burden of countering with evidence a prima facie case made against that party. William D. Hawkland, *Uniform Commercial Code Series* § 2A-516:08 (1984)."

The above fragments describe different aspects of the burden of proof from different points of view. However, analysis of these fragments taken together fully confirms the essential points of its understanding already identified in previous editions of the Black's dictionary. Namely, this confirms the *binary structure* of the burden of proof, and, accordingly, of appropriate concept (and term) that grasps it. By means of this concept, one thinks about two necessary things. First, it is the obligation of logical-rhetorical-legal persuasion that is aimed to get the requisite degree of relevant belief of jury, judges, etc.; a party wishes to succeed must never refuse to complete this obligation (the burden of persuasion). Second, it is the party's duty to participate in litigation and to bring evidence in favor of its position orderly, in accordance with def-

system, a feature of which is the key icon ⇄, is used to refer to the original legal documents.

inite rules (the burden of production, the burden of going forward with the evidence). In addition, concept of the burden of proof in general case includes a warning about the risk of nonpersuasion, which will entail a party's failure to achieve its aim ultimately¹⁰.

At the very end of the article, there is a following fragment concerning the burden of proof.

"middle burden of proof. A party's duty to prove a fact by clear and convincing evidence. This standard lies between the preponderance-of-the-evidence standard and the beyond-a-reasonable-doubt standard. See *clear and convincing evidence* under EVIDENCE. [Cases: Evidence ⇔ 596.]" (Black H.C. 2009 : 223).

Thus, the burden of proof and, accordingly, the concept and term that grasp it, are recognized as situational in sense that they depend on the adoption of one or the other standard of proof. This, in turn, is determined by the nature of cases under consideration (criminal, civil, etc.).

Conclusions

The research article devoted to different means of understanding and speech expression of the burden of proof in Anglo-American law. This one is a part of broader discussion about the phenomenon of legal proof.

In the article, firstly, two interconnected sets of concepts and corresponding terms that grasp the burden of proof directly are fixed. In a first approximation, omitting analogous ones, seems reasonable to add to the very term "burden of proof" the cluster of terms, which includes, on the one hand, "truth" or "belief", "burden of persuasion", "risk of nonpersuasion", and, on the other hand, "burden of production" or "burden of going forward with the evidence", "*prima facie* case" and "order of proof".

Secondly, it is clear that understanding and expression of the burden of proof vary greatly depending on recognition of one or the other legal standard of proof.

Thirdly, it is strongly emphasized that understanding of the burden of proof has evolved and is

currently functioning in the three dimensions: legal, rhetorical, and logical. These ones complement dimensions of space and time that are natural for any human activity.

Fourthly, it is advisable to take into account contemporary comprehension of the logical dimension. According to it, the logical dimension not only unites the logical and dialectical, which Aristotle divided, but also embraces both demonstrative and nondemonstrative kinds of reasoning. If one takes into account at least these circumstances, it is not difficult to recognize in general case the probabilistic nature of the result of fulfilling the burden of proof and, therefore, the inevitability of idea of risk of nonpersuasion in its understanding. In addition, the probabilistic nature of even here-and-now successful completion by a party its burden of proof does not preclude the possibility of a legal error arising because of a sincere mistake or a true false.

Fifthly, this article proposes an assumption: it seems possible to extrapolate the conclusion on legal-rhetorical-logical multidimensionality of concept of the burden of proof to the whole set of concepts (and terms) that grasps legal proof, including the concept of proof beyond a reasonable doubt. If so, any attempt to reduce definitions of elements of this cluster, in particular – of concept of proof beyond a reasonable doubt, to pure logical definitions will be unsuccessful in general case. The multidimensionality of concept of proof beyond a reasonable doubt seems to be an actual source of well-known difficulty to unify practical explanation as well as using of standard of proof beyond a reasonable doubt.

Competing interests

This study did not receive any financial support. I believe that there are no conflicts of interest related to this article.

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¹⁰ Search for indisputable truth or operation with it can be a part of specific process of persuasion. However, one should not forget that in general case legal persuasion is not obliged to meet pure logical standard of proof beyond any doubt. Such persuasion (and resulting degree of the belief) must meet one or other legal standard of proof, remaining only more or less probabilistic by nature in fact. Therefore, there is a natural risk of nonpersuasion and of non-acceptance of correspondent belief.

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